

Vertical Innovations in Transport And Logistics over 5G experimentation facilities

D6.5 Report on Standardization - Intermediate

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
5G-PPP	5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership
6G-IA	6G Smart Networks and Services Industry Association
AAP	Alternative Approval Process
ARIB	The Association of Radio Industries and Businesses
ATIS	The Alliance for Telecommunications Industry Solutions
CCSA	China Communications Standards Association
CIS	Container Infrastructure Services
CISM	Container Infrastructure Services and Services Management
C-ITS	Co-operative ITS
DCSA	Digital Container Shipping Association
DTLF	Digital Transport and Logistics Forum (DTLF)
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
GA	Grant Agreement
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
HILME	Hellenic Institute for Logistics Management
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
ISG	Industry Specification Group
ITS	Intelligent Transport System

ITU	International Telecommunication Union
MANO	Management and Orchestration
MEC	Multi-Access Edge Computing
NFV	Network Function Virtualization
NFVI	NFV infrastructure
NFVO	Network Function Virtualization Orchestrator
PE	Public Enquiry
SA	Service and System Aspects
SDO	Standards Development Organization
T&L	Transport & Logistics
TC	Technical Committee
TSDSI	Telecommunications Standards Development Society
TSG	Technical Specification Group
TTA	Telecommunications Technology Association
TTC	Telecommunication Technology Committee
VIM	Virtual Infrastructure Managers
VNF	Virtual and Containerized Network Functions
QoE	Quality of Experience
SMP	Standards Making Process
WG	Work Groups

1. Executive Summary

The scope of this deliverable is to issue a mid-term report on the standardization activities performed by the VITAL-5G consortium during the first half of the project, in line with **Objective 6**, sustained by the effort of accelerating the adoption and scale-up of VITAL-5G Facility and Network Applications, by providing contributions to key pre-standardisations and standardizations organisations, as VITAL-5G is expected to impact the standardization within several SDOs as **3GPP**, **ETSI**, **IETF** or **ITU-T** and pre-SDOs as **5G-PPP** and **6G-IA**.

For this re-submitted deliverable, the reviewers' comments have been taken into consideration and the structure of the document has been adapted to respond to requirements. Improved standardization contributions will be provided in the next deliverable, to be submitted by M42.

As the VITAL-5G architecture is continuously taking shape, mainly based on the achievements and progress received from WP1, WP2 and WP3, we are able to identify VITAL-5G components that could constitute interest for standardization.

To better understand the standardization landscape, we have bolstered our focus towards the monitoring of the existing VITAL-5G's relevant standardization landscape in general, while also focusing in particular on the T&L and 5G sectors. We also monitored the evolution of different SDOs with relevant impact on VITAL-5G to keep aligned the developed features and software components with the most recent standardization outcomes, as for example the 3GPP Features for Rel.16, integration needs based on the novel interfaces and APIs implemented.

Considering the initial objectives, set out in the project Description of Work and added based on the received recommendation and inputs during the 1st project phase, the goals and objectives achieved by this task are, as it can be seen in the deliverable:

- i. Identification of the pertinent and crucial innovations of VITAL-5G that can be standardized.
- ii. Development of concrete methodologies for converting the innovations into standards contributions.
- iii. The opportunities for project-wide submissions to different standardization development organizations (SDOs) as well as national certification authorities and Working groups (E.g.: 3GPP, ETSI, IETF, ITU).
- iv. The coordination of contributions across Standards Development Organizations (SDOs) and industry forums.
- v. A follow-up of the VITAL-5G partners to maximize the success with the standardization efforts (Final Report).
- vi. * Monitoring of Standardization Organizations activities (seminars/webinars, conferences, publications, workshops, etc.). (*Objective added after Project Review in 2021).

The document is structured in four parts, each covering the following subjects: Standardization Landscape, Standardization Methodology, Standardization Monitoring, Standardization Contributions.

The document closes with a Conclusions section in which we summarize the work of the current deliverable as well as our objectives for the next standardization deliverable.

For sake of clarity, this deliverable presents the work achieved through several SDOs monitoring and state-of-the-art analysis, active participation of **VITAL-5G at OSM 13 Ecosystem Day**, **ETSI NFV Plugtests 2021** and **5GPPP Pre-Standardization Group**, with relevant participation within **Software Network and Architecture Working Groups**¹, in a detailed contribution described in [26].

¹ <https://5g-ppp.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/10/Software-Network-WG-Network-Applications-2022.pdf>
<https://5g-ppp.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/11/Architecture-WP-V4.0-final.pdf>

2. Introduction

This deliverable reports the activities related to the standardization activities and effort carried out during the 1st project phase, also specifying the next actions that will continue by the end of the project.

VITAL-5G plans to utilize the opportunity of having some of its consortium members working actively in Standards Development Organizations (SDOs) in propagating and standardizing technological developments that can be achieved through results from the different aspects of the project. The VITAL-5G’s consortium is made up of partners with varieties of expertise in technology and scientific research with different level of presence in the standardization community. VITAL-5G will follow a comprehensive standardization plan to better monitor, identify and then contribute to important international standardization bodies as well as to benefit disseminating its results to the technology community at large through a range of dissemination channels. The focus around the VITAL-5G project outcomes, the novel techniques related to 5G and T&L sector as crucial innovation, coordination with the existing relevant SDOs’ outputs and industry overall requirements and development planning are key actions implemented by VITAL-5G consortium. In VITAL-5G we are integrating multiple network technologies and 3GPP Rel.16 features, including RAN, Core and EDGE technologies, building the E2E full experimentation and testing methodology for Network Applications validation. Within this complex and highly demanding network and services deployment, we have identified few points where the project could bring benefits through standardization. There have been identified several risks related to our proposal for the standardization process, as for example the different SDOs fragmentation and divergences across the industries, as in VITAL-5G we are trying to align the technology and the industries approaches into a coherent and practical implementation of the 5G infrastructure, influencing the standardization processes in the area of interest identified.

2.1. Mapping VITAL-5G Outputs

The purpose of this section is to map VITAL-5G’s Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project’s respective outputs and work performed.

Table 1: Adherence to VITAL-5G’s GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

GA Component Title	GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
TASKS			
T 6.2 – Standardization Contributions	<p>The opportunities for project-wide submissions to different standardization development organizations (SDOs) as well as national certification authorities and Working groups (E.g.: 3GPP, ETSI, IETF, ITU).</p> <p>The coordination of contributions across Standardization</p>	<p>2 Standardization Landscape</p> <p>5 Standardization Contributions to SDOs</p>	<p>Planned in the initial Description of Action.</p> <p>Identifying the most important SDOs in the 5G and T&L sectors.</p>

	Development Organizations (SDOs) and industry forums.		
T 6.2 – Standardization Monitoring	The monitoring of SDOs activities with focus on the 5G and T&L Use Cases .	6 Standardization Organizations Monitoring	Included after 1 st Year Review. By monitoring the most important 5G and T&L SDOs we as a consortium will be aware of what innovations in these verticals become standards while also learning insights on standardization methodology, trends and evolution in these sectors.
T 6.2 – Standardization Contributions	The development of concrete methodologies for converting the innovations into standards contributions.	3 Standardization Methodologies	Planned in the initial Description of Action. Elaborates on various methodologies to be used in the process of standardization in general, in the 5G or T&L sectors. Some of these methodologies can be used in the submission of our future standardization proposals (both in this project or in future projects).
T 6.2 – Standardization Contributions	The identification of the pertinent and crucial innovations of VITAL-5G that need to be standardized .	5 Standardization Contributions to SDOs	Planned in the initial Description of Action. Implies the entire consortium to scan for components with innovation potential within the VITAL-5G Platform (e.g., a novel data transmission model, new parameters in a network component, new architectures, etc.), taking that component through a standardization process (selecting a methodology, elaborating the proposal and submitting it to an SDO).
DELIVERABLE			
Deliverable 6.5 – Report on Standardization Activities – Intermediate.			
Its scope is to provide up to date information regarding SDOs activities in the 5G and T&L sector, while also trying to identify potential innovation within the project that could be considered for standardization submission to a Standardization Organization.			

2.2. Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

This deliverable defines the goal in the standardization area in line with the specific project tasks and activities by identifying the actual progress in the SDO's area and by influencing all this achievement through the project's relevant outputs.

The deliverable is addressing the objectives addressed by the task, sustained by the 1st half project results and outputs, defined by:

- Standardization Landscape
 - Provides descriptions of existing SDOs that shape the landscape of 5G and T&L standards with the scope of describing relevant 5G and T&L Organizations and identifying Standardization Organizations Workgroups that have relevant activity for the VITAL-5G project.
- Standardization Methodology
 - Describes the methodology agreed between partners to be used for a future standardization proposal. To be more specific, the scope is to describe the Standardization Methodology of existing SDOs, raise partners awareness with regard to the standardization process and ease the standardization proposal submission process.
- Standardization Organizations Monitoring
 - The monitoring of SDOs is performed by the participation of consortium members to various SDOs events or in their Work Groups. The scope here is to follow, participate and report on relevant 5G and T&L Organizations activities: workshops, webinars while focusing on project relevant Workgroups workshops, webinars, publications, etc.
- Standardization Contributions to SDOs
 - Describes the identified technical elements of the VITAL-5G platform that could be submitted as a standardization proposal and the standardization proposal itself (if available at the time of writing). To recap, the goals here are: identifying a project element that could be standardized, describe it from different architecture perspectives, describe the underlying standard, identify an SDO WG to which the Standardization Proposal can be submitted and describe the standard submission procedure of that specific WG.

3. Standardization Landscape

The objective is to focus on describing the existing Standardization Landscape of interest for this project, mainly related to the main 5G and T&L standardization organizations, listing their role, focus and implication in standardization related activities (effort considered towards a state-of-the-art analysis).

3.1. 5G Standardization Organizations

This chapter focuses on describing the existing Standardization Landscape from a 5G standpoint, describing some of the main standardization organizations that activate in the 5G space and focusing more on the relevant organizations for the VITAL-5G project.

3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP)

The 3GPP was established in 1998 by seven regional Standards Development Organizations (SDOs), including ETSI, and comprises more than 600 members. Its scope is to produce applicable reports and specifications for a third-generation mobile system based on evolved Global System for mobile communication core networks and radio access technologies. It aims to provide system specifications for radio access, core and transport. It looks at service capabilities and quality.

The 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) unites seven telecommunications standard development organizations (ARIB, ATIS, CCSA, ETSI, TSDSI, TTA, TTC), known as “Organizational Partners” and provides their members with a stable environment to produce the Reports and Specifications that define 3GPP technologies. Its focus is mostly on radio telecommunications.

3GPP aims to produce technical specifications and reports comprised in the 3GPP working procedure which is maintained up-to-date with the evolution of the radio communications from 3G onwards. The major focus for all 3GPP Releases is to make the system backwards and forwards compatible where possible, to ensure that the operation of user equipment is uninterrupted. The fifth working group (SA-WG5 or SA5) of the 3GPP TSG-SA, named Telecom Management is dealing with the requirements, architecture and solutions for provisioning and management of the network elements and network services. Additionally, SA5 will define charging solutions in alignment with the related charging requirements developed by the relevant WGs and will specify the architecture and protocols for charging of the network and its services. The most relevant 5G studies from the SA5 enabling the first phase in 3GPP Release 15 includes building up a new service-oriented management architecture, network slicing and all the necessary functionalities for management and charging for 5G networks.

The current work within SA5 influences the currently used 3GPP Release 16 as the target of our deployments in VITAL-5G and includes several other work items such as management of QoE measurement collection and new technologies for RESTful management protocols.

Another relevant Working Group for the VITAL-5G project is SA6 (Application Enablement and Critical Communication Applications), which is dedicated to the definition of application layer architecture specifications for 3GPP verticals. The related outcomes, e.g., in terms of architecture requirements, deployment models, and information flows to enable and support vertical applications through specialized service frameworks, have been carefully considered to drive the design of the VITAL-5G platform features for Network Application management and as enablers of the interaction between Network Applications and 5G network. The importance of 3GPP within the VITAL-5G project is of crucial importance as all 3 testbeds are based on 3GPP 5G SA Rel. 16 standardized architectures and elements.

European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI)

ETSI is a recognized European Standardization Organization and aims to develop a strategy for a wide range of areas socio-economic, policy making and technology trends. Going from economy, sustainability to industrial strategy it takes a technology-driven perspective. ETSI also focuses on innovation in information and communication technology going from artificial intelligence to cloud to quantum computing. ETSI is inclusive in of a global community, of all industry and society sectors, favouring collaboration and promoting the knowledge of standards. Aside from focusing on emerging and developing technologies, it also tries to cover the end-to-end perspective.

The mission of ETSI is to provide platforms where interested parties can collaborate on the development and promotion of standards in ICT, used globally to benefit all. ETSI wants to address global challenges such as sustainable development, modernization, climate change or social cohesion. It does so through standardization which in turn is an enabler for an interoperable and conducive business environment. A generally accepted technical basis can drive innovation across multiple verticals.

ETSI is addressing digital literacy that in turn will help people adopt new technologies. It is also driven by the need to limit waste and pollution, maintain products for a longer life cycle and regenerate natural systems.

In terms of organization, there are several technical groups which include the technical committee, ETSI projects, ETSI partnership projects, industry specifications groups, special committees, and task forces. The General Assembly is the highest decision-making authority, and it supports the various committees.

This SDO and its subsequent Working Groups (WGs), but especially the orchestration-oriented information is important for the VITAL-5G project considering that all 3 project testbeds are using as NFVOs ETSI based MANO systems.

The ETSI NFV ISG (Industry Specification Group) is the main standardization organization behind the development of requirements and technical specifications for the network functions virtualization (NFV) enabling technology. NFV comprises all enabling mechanisms about network functions softwarization and virtualization; hence, needs a strong standard development organization for developing its functional requirements as well as technical specifications especially for the information and communication technology industry. ETSI NFV Industry Specification Group (ISG) is primarily designated to carry out the standardization functionalities, which include the development of standard architectural frameworks and technical specifications documentation to enable an open concept of NFV that incorporates interoperability between different virtualization technologies and creates a healthy commercial NFV ecosystem.

International Telecommunication Union (ITU)

The International Telecommunication Union (ITU), headquartered in Geneva, Switzerland, is the United Nations specialized agency for telecommunications. It focuses on three areas radiocommunications, economic development and telecommunications.

In terms of leadership, the ITU plenipotentiary conference is the top policy making body. The conference takes place every four years to adopt five-year strategic plans. The ITU council, in the interval between the plenipotentiary conferences, deals with broad policies and ensures the daily running of the union. The administrative entities are the World Standardization Assembly focused on general policy and the Standardization advisory group dealing with review priorities, programs, and operations.

ITU has been active since 1865 and aims to ensure the efficient and on time production of high-quality standards covering all fields of telecommunications. Over 3000 recommendations have been provided by ITU and the recommendations are being approved within six weeks of completion.

ITU-T is currently addressing the standards needs for the 21st century in areas such as:

- Next-generation networks (NGN);
- Broadband access;
- Multimedia services;
- Emergency telecommunications;
- IP issues;
- Optical networking;
- Network management;
- Internet governance;
- ICT security issues;
- Fixed/mobile convergence.

The recommendations can be normative divided by series and non-normative to include handbooks, guidelines and supplements. The operational bulleting represents an update, at every two weeks meant to maintain the interconnection of the telecommunication networks by keeping up-to-date routing plans and numbering. Study groups, which may include working parties or rapporteur groups for specific projects, publish the technical work and various other publications. The projects or questions address technical studies and focus on the contributions. Contributions can be submitted by mail or web [1].

ITU has two types of members, either member of national governments or sector members represented by companies from the private sector. One can also participate as an associate from the private sector. As a member, one can participate in the development of the ICT standards, understand future technologies and work with leading vendors and companies.

The Telecommunication standardization sector of the ITU, ITU-T, is basically saddled with the responsibility of developing standardization documentations for telecommunication services using specially created study groups. The different study groups study a particular technology and come up with standard documents (ITU-T Recommendations). Some relevant activities have been carried out in the area of NFV energy efficiency support within both ETSI and ITU-T. In ETSI most of the actions are focused on the Environmental Engineering Technical Committee (EETC).

The first one is related to the evolution of the Green Abstraction Layer (GAL) ETSI Standard (ETSI ES 203 237) for supporting the new virtualized network capabilities, i.e., NFV environment, giving an effective and standard way (interfaces) to manage and possibly optimize the energy consumption. The second one is related to the support of a Huawei initiative for the L. NFV standard proposal entitled "Measurement method for energy efficiency of Network Functions Virtualization", which gives a framework for laboratory evaluation of the virtualized network functions.

5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership (5G-PPP)

The 5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership (5G-PPP) is a joint initiative between the European Commission and European ICT industry (ICT manufacturers, telecommunications operators, service providers, SMEs, and researcher Institutions) that will allow for fast, efficient, and easy service delivery anywhere in the world.

From a high-level perspective, the 5G PPP delivers solutions, architectures, technologies, and standards for the ubiquitous next generation communication infrastructures of the coming decade.

The 5G PPP expects telecom and IT to be combined into a common infrastructure that can support both fixed and mobile access in ten years. The hardware will be based on general purpose, reprogrammable and specific high-performance hardware that will offer resources for transportation, routing, storage and execution. Network elements will become like equipment that gathers computing resources, interface and functions based on virtualization technologies.

Ensuring interoperability, economies of scale, and affordable cost for system deployment requires the emergence of globally accepted standards. The goal of the partnership is to have European industry driving the development of 5G standards.

Providing 1000 times higher wireless area capacity and more varied service capabilities are indicative of new network characteristics to be achieved at an operational level. It is possible to save a lot of energy. The main source of energy consumption in mobile communication networks is the radio access network. Currently, 90 hours is the average for service creation. Zero perceived downtime for services provision is achieved by creating a reliable and secure internet. Over 7 trillion wireless devices serve 7 billion people. A Scalable Management Framework will enable fast deployment of novel applications, including sensor-based applications, with a reduction of the network management OPEX by at least 20%.

The 5G infrastructure public private partnership delivers solutions, architectures, technologies and standards for the next generation communication infrastructures. It is focused on innovations in the European industry in particular communications, energy and data security.

5G PPP is looking at designing with high flexibility and a service driven approach for the delivery of converged services preserving security and privacy across a versatile architecture with unified control of any type of ICT resources. In this regard, the aim is to develop networks that support high throughput and low latency for sensors, IoT data transfer or mission critical services. The effort towards digitalization of vertical markets is also an objective in the scope of 5GPPP developments.

One of the approaches of 5GPPP is that, going forward, the infrastructure should be virtualized, programmable and supported by high performance hardware. 5G will integrate telecom, compute and storage resources into one programmable and unified infrastructure which will allow for an optimized usage of all distributed resources in a sustainable and scalable manner. Through energy efficiency, the aim for cost reduction and sustainability will also be reached.

Within the 5GPPP, we have identified the following Workgroups that could be of interest for our standardization efforts, as they are relevant to VITALital-5G technical concepts such as: orchestration, virtualization, platform monitoring. These are: Open Smart Networks and Services WG, 5G/Beyond 5G Architecture WG, Software Networks WG, Network Management & QoS WG. Also, the consortium has members in most of the above WGs so standardization related topics can be communicated and monitored more easily. Concrete contributions of the VITAL-5G project to the 5G PPP activities are detailed in VITAL-5G D 6.8 Report on 5G PPP collaboration activities.

3.2. Transport & Logistics Standardization Organizations

We have identified the following T&L SDOs or SDO Work Groups are relevant to the VITAL-5G project, considered main bodies of interest for our scope and listed further.

IEEE P1950.1 STANDARD FOR COMMUNICATIONS ARCHITECTURAL FUNCTIONAL FRAMEWORK FOR SMART CITIES (focusing on smart mobility)

Orange Romania has joined the P1950.1 Standard for communications architectural functional framework for smart cities work group in February 2022. BEIA also participates from the consortium. The workgroup reviews several areas such as ecosystems, networks and governance with the aim to define certain guidelines for smart cities.

The focus of the framework is on the interdisciplinary points between more ecosystems and the extraction of common points that would apply to smart cities. One does not limit itself to a certain ecosystem or certain rules within those ecosystems, but rather the scope is to discern the common denominator. There are certain aspects

that are reviewed recurrently when discussing ecosystems such as the ones related to utilities or security and other basic needs for a city to function properly.

Also, in terms of networks, it is out of scope to refer to a specific technology, but rather to define the criteria which differentiate a smart city from a regular one. User management and network operations are reviewed and several frameworks such as ITIL or TMForum are considered. When referring to networks, the group refers to various types of interconnections be them in telecommunications or in transport and logistics.

Governance or more broadly the ESG (Environment, Sustainability or Social aspects and Governance) has 3 functions: strategic, tactical and operations. The work group aims to assess all these functions in more detail and define what is within and outside of the scope when describing a smart city. Security, sustainability, environment preservation, digital literacy, citizen accountability, resiliency, disaster recovery are all topics reviewed by this group.

HILME (“Hellenic Institute for Logistics Management”) affiliated to International Logistics Associations, ESTI INT

HILME (Hellenic Institute of Logistics Management), is a non-profitable organization aiming at the increase of logistics management effectiveness in Trade and Industry, as well as, in the Public and Private sector through the reinforcement of a coordinated approach to the distribution materials, the quality management and the after-sales customer service.

HILME was founded in 1994 addressing the growth potential of this sector, as well as the need to support and upgrade professionals active in logistics to the benefit of the Hellenic market and the national economy very early on. In this context, HILME has developed a strategic cooperation with the European Logistics Association (ELA), which constitutes the largest and most important Logistics organization in Europe, officially represented in Greece by HILME.

HILME is a full member of the ELA with active and dynamic participation in international conferences, in work visits to cargo and logistics hubs (logistics cities), the evaluation of the ELA AWARDS as well as in the planning, organization and implementation of the ELA Certification for Logisticians (ECBL). The HILME is also in cooperation with the Logistics Association of Crete (LAC) and the Cyprus Logistics Association (CLA).

The HILME has set the following Goals:

- Establish logistics standards and specifications.
- Complete ELA Logistics Training and Certification in Greece.
- Promote Extroversion and Synergies towards stressing the high level of Greek logistics in the global market.
- Promotion and Distinction on a European level through the European Award for Logistics Excellence. Networking/Updating of new technologies in logistics.
- Mentoring/Coaching Program.

DIAKINIS follows specific workgroups within HILME while WINGS as technology provider follows the HILME events for liaison and exploitation purposes. Lykourgos Manoliadis (DIA, Deputy Manager) follows HILME activities and participates in all monthly meetings as a member. Also, he has participated as a speaker in the last conferences, namely the Logi.C 21 - City Logistics [Figure 1](#)) the 5th International Logistics Forum & Supply Chain Day ([Figure 2](#)), and the Logi.C 22 Urban Connected Supply Chains ([Figure 3](#)).

Logi.C 21 ΠΑΝΕΛΛΗΝΙΟ ΣΥΝΕΔΡΙΟ
 LOGISTICS CONFERENCES Αστικές Εμπορευματικές Μεταφορές (City Logistics) & Βράβευση Εργασιών Βραβείου Μεταφορών Ε.Ε.Σ.Υ.Μ «Δημήτριος Τσαμπούλας» 2020 & 2021

Υπό την Αιγίδα:

ΕΛΛΗΝΙΚΗ ΔΗΜΟΚΡΑΤΙΑ
 ΥΠΟΥΡΓΕΙΟ ΥΠΟΔΟΜΩΝ ΚΑΙ ΜΕΤΑΦΟΡΩΝ

ΕΛΛΗΝΙΚΗ ΔΗΜΟΚΡΑΤΙΑ
 ΥΠΟΥΡΓΕΙΟ ΝΑΥΤΙΛΙΑΣ & ΝΗΣΙΩΤΙΚΗΣ ΠΟΛΙΤΙΚΗΣ

Figure 1: Logi.C 21 - the banner.

Figure 2: 5th International Logistics Forum & Supply Chain Day – the banner.

Figure 3: Logi.C 22 - the banner.

ETSI - TECHNICAL COMMITTEE (TC) INTELLIGENT TRANSPORT SYSTEMS (ITS)

ETSI TC ITS is responsible for standardization to support the development and implementation of Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS) service provision across the network, for transport networks, vehicles and transport users, including interface aspects, multiple modes of transport and interoperability between systems and helps to accelerate the introduction of ITS services and applications and to maximize their benefits by developing common European standards and technical specifications to enable interoperability.

TC ITS is leading the drive to achieve international standard by developing and maintaining standards, specifications and other deliverables to support the implementation of ITS Service provision for transport networks, vehicles and transport users, including interface aspects and multiple modes of transport and interoperability between systems.

The workgroup is developing global standards for Co-operative ITS (C-ITS), where vehicles exchange information with other road users and the surrounding infrastructure. Applications include road safety, traffic control, fleet management and location-based services, driver assistance, hazard warnings, support for emergency services – and ultimately the realization of fully autonomous driving.

Their standards provide support for a wide range of services and applications including Cooperative Adaptive Cruise Control, Congestion Control, Cooperative Awareness, Perception and Maneuver Coordination, and Decentralized Environmental Notification (DEN) to alert road users. In addition, TC ITS develops conformance test specifications which are crucial for the commercial deployment of the technology and are closely involved in radio spectrum requirements for ITS. TC ITS is structured on a set of Working Groups (WGs), namely:

- ITS WG1: Application requirements and services
- ITS WG2: Architecture and cross layers
- ITS WG3: Transport and network
- ITS WG4: Media and medium related
- ITS WG5: Security

Digital Container Shipping Association

The role of the Digital Container Shipping Association (DCSA) is to establish IT standards that would enable interoperability of technology solutions across the industry. The purpose is to facilitate digital interconnectivity and seamless data communication that anyone who touches the industry can leverage. DCSA standards are

developed in close conjunction with the member carriers who validate, align and agree to them and work with DCSA to ensure widespread adoption.

The Digital Container Shipping Association (DCSA) is a nonprofit, autonomous association built up in 2019 by a few of the biggest holder shipping companies. DCSA's mission is to be the de facto standards body for the industry, setting the technological foundation for interoperable IT systems. Working together with carriers, DCSA is continuously developing vendor-neutral, technology-agnostic, guidelines for IT and non-competitive commerce entities. By working towards the broad selection of these measures, their scope is to move the industry forward in terms of client encounter, effectiveness, collaboration, advancement, and regard for the environment.

Collaboration between T&L companies is crucial for achieving greater efficiency and agility to meet new demands. Currently, fragmented systems are holding back T&L industry inter-operability. A cornerstone for this is the seamless, end-to-end exchange of information which will permit various segregated technologies to better communicate with one another and provide relevant macro-level data about the T&L sector.

One of the scopes of DCSA is the establishment of standards for a unified technology foundation that enables global collaboration while making shipping services easy to use, flexible, efficient, reliable, and environmentally friendly.

Improving data flow in container shipping for good cargo flow, customer experience and sustainability through collaboration is the joint vision of DCSA and its members. Developing and adopting digital standards for non-competitive IT practices is core to our work. Watch the video to get an idea about how excited and committed DCSA and subject matter experts from ocean carriers are to work on standards for some of the most urgent and impactful needs in the industry.

At macro level, we have the FIT Alliance which is a body with the mission to standardize the digitalization of international trade. Members are: DCSA BIMCO, FIATA ICC and SWIFT and its scope is to raise awareness about the importance of common and interoperable platforms data standards operation and common legislative conditions across international jurisdictions. The aim is to facilitate acceptance and adoption of an eBL by regulators, banks, and insurers and to unify communication between these organizations and customers, physical and contractual carriers, and all other stakeholders involved in an international trade transaction.

Digital Transport and Logistics Forum

The Digital Transport and Logistics Forum (DTLF), is an expert group of the European Commission bringing together public and private stakeholders from various transport and logistics communities to support the European Commission in promoting the digital transformation of the transport and logistics sector.

The DTLF provides a platform for structural dialogue, provision of technical expertise, cooperation and coordination between the Commission, Member States and the transport and logistic sector. Its goal is to assist the Commission in the development and implementation of the Union's relevant activities and programs, in particular those targeted at full-scale digital interoperability and data exchange in a shared, secured and trusted transport and logistics dataspace.

The DTLF's overall objective is full-scale digital interoperability and data exchange in a shared, secured and trusted transport and logistics dataspace. For this purpose, the DTLF splits currently into two strands of work organized under two subgroups.

The group has received two mandates (the first one ended in 2018 and the second is still undergoing). Since 2018, under its second mandate, the DTLF continues to discuss and build consensus on the necessary technical, organizational and legal principles. Its organization is demonstrated in Figure 4. Subgroups are dedicated to specific topics defined in work programs and will be discontinued and/or replaced once completed.

Figure 4: Organization of the DTLF.

One of its main roles is to provide and enforce more efficient freight transport rules in the Union, by facilitating risk-based controls and ensuring the availability of more data of high and standardized quality that could be used for monitoring and statistical purposes, among others.

International Maritime Organization

The International Maritime Organization is an organization of the United Nations that was established in 1948, active from 1959, with Headquarters in London which has as its main objectives to develop and maintain comprehensive and relevant standards on maritime safety, security and freight shipping internationally.

Over 175 of States are part of this organization and it continues to shape the way that maritime shipping is performed at a global level.

As a specialized agency of the United Nations, IMO is the global standard-setting authority for the safety, security and environmental performance of international shipping. Its main role is to create a regulatory framework for the shipping industry that is fair and effective, universally adopted and universally implemented.

IMO measures cover all aspects of international shipping – including ship design, construction, equipment, manning, operation and disposal – to ensure that this VITAL sector remains safe, environmentally sound, energy efficient and secure.

The IMO is also involved in legal issues matters pertaining to international shipping, such as liability and compensation matters, and facilitating of international maritime traffic. The Assembly, the IMO's governing body, meets every two years to address issues in international shipping, and looks at the organization's budget. We believe that knowledge gained through our participation in its activities will be valuable in the submission of a rigorous standardization proposal and its success.

GS1 Transport & Logistics

GS1 is the global standard-setting organization for logistics, commerce, and supply chain:

- Standardizes the issuance of various identifiers (for products and goods, palettes and containers, locations and organizations, etc.)
- Organizes the allocation of identifiers (barcodes and RFIDs)
- Defines product classifications
- Creates data models for events in supply chains, and for describing products

GS1 standards cover the following areas:

- Identify
- Capture

- Share

They are of interest to us as the global standard for T&L tasks and specifically because the EPCIS sub-family of standard are used to track shipments and describe sensor readings as supplied by the EGTN IoT Infrastructure from sensors deployed by project partners.

The following materials provide useful introductions to GS1 standards:

- (1) The GS1 Glossary defines important terms and concepts in GS1 standards and data schemas and
- (2) The GS1 Discovery App is an interactive web application that highlights the use of GS1 standards in various supply chains and situations. For example, it can show information about applicable standards to the supply chain operation.

4. Standardization Organizations Monitoring

The scope of this chapter, as agreed after the VITAL-5G Year 1 review, is to monitor the activities of relevant standardization organizations in both the 5G and T&L landscape, identifying standardization activities of these bodies, monitoring their Work Groups' activities, by participating in their public or private standardization related events in order to identify the standardization related trends in both the 5G and T&L industries.

This will provide the project with valuable information as to what previously non-standard or innovative industry concepts are becoming standard architecture elements which should help the project to possibly use some of these standardized elements as blueprints for actual components to be implemented within the VITAL-5G architecture while also providing insights on what existing components of the VITAL-5G platform could be standardized.

In order to better illustrate the contribution to SDO monitoring activities of partners in the VITAL-5G consortium, Table 2 provides insights into partners' monitoring activities and sections where these activities are described in more detail.

Table 2: VITAL-5G SDO Monitoring Activities.

SDO Monitoring Activity	Contributors	Comments – Contribution Description
4.1. Monitoring of 5G SDOs		
Participation in 5G SDO events relevant to the VITAL-5G project / platform components.		
4.1.1. ITU – AI in 5G and forthcoming 6G: Standardization and Regulatory Perspectives	ORO	Updated Consortium know-how on Dynamic Resource Allocation and Dynamic Network Slicing using AI techniques.
4.1.2. StandICT – 7th Talk & Walk Webinar on Women in ICT Standards	ORO	Obtained information on how to write a draft of a standard for a future standardization proposal.
4.1.3. 5G-SOLUTIONS - Broadcaster Standardization Workshop	ORO	Illustrates various 5G E2E elements that are being standardized helping us better understand the various aspects of the entire standardization process while also providing valuable information on the new features of future 3GPP releases.
4.1.4. 5G-SOLUTIONS - Standardization Online Workshop	ORO	This 5G-SOLUTIONS workshop focuses on subjects of interest for the VITAL-5G standardization efforts, such as: identification and management of a deterministic slice, API exposure of Network Management Functions, Orchestration by the network operator on multiple clients' environments.
4.1.5. OSM13 Ecosystem Day	NXW	Presented the seamless integration between the VITAL-5G platform and OSM using Network Application logic on data models and platform components. Provisioning and lifecycle management were performed using standardized APIs – of interest for our standardization efforts.

4.1.6. ETSI NFV Plugtests 2021	ORO	Observe the latest VNF, NFV, NFVO, VIM, NFVI and MEC platforms, systems and tools all in one place, in an integration exercise. This elps the VITAL-5G consortium adopt proper integration interface types and techniques between platform components.
4.1.7. 5GPPP – 5G European Annual Journal 2021	ORO	Standardization Organization monitoring activity by which the project consortium is learning from other success stories of other EU projects regarding their successful standardization initiatives.
4.1.8. Merging 5Gi and 3GPP specifications	ORO	Observe 3GPP standards evolution in future releases (in this case non-standard wireless frequencies became standard).
4.2. Monitoring of Transport & Logistics SDOs		
Participation in T&L SDO events, relevant to the VITAL-5G project / platform components.		
4.2.1. Digital Container Shipping Association Track and Trace Standards	ORO	The Track & Trace standardized APIs resemble the APIs that we are in the process of developing between the VITAL-5G platform and the subsequent testbeds. It is a learning opportunity for the design of our own standardized API components.
4.2.2. GS1 Identifiers: Tag Data Standard	ORO	Learn from existing standardized APIs in the T&L sector for the standardization of our own VITAL-5G platform components integration APIs.
4.2.3. GS1 Global Product Classification	ORO	Learn from existing standardized APIs in the T&L sector for the standardization of our own APIs.
4.2.4. EPCIS and CBV	EBOS, ORO	These are standardized methods for product movement through the supply chain. Documenting on its' T&L APIs provides us with info on how to make our own VITAL-5G platform components integration APIs between components as “flexible” / compatible as possible.

4.1. Monitoring of 5G SDOs

In this subchapter the focus is on monitoring the activities of the 5G related SDOs, the main focus being on the largest of these organizations.

From the start of the task, the VITAL-5G consortium has followed the standardization related activities of the following standardization organizations, namely 3GPP, ETSI, ITU, 5G PPP.

For both the monitoring part and possible standardization initiative of the VITAL-5G project, our current approach is to participate at standardization related events of these organizations and participate in focus groups (open to any telecom industry company) or even in existing SDO work groups. In the following, we report the list

of initiatives we followed or events (webinars or meetings) we attended for the purpose of monitoring specific standardization efforts of particular interest for the project.

4.1.1. ITU – ‘AI in 5G and forthcoming 6G: Standardization and Regulatory Perspectives

The webinar is focused on the relevance of the AI ecosystem and its relevance for 5G networks within multiple cross-industry Use Cases.

Insights on the impact of AI on 5G and upcoming 6G networks are presented by Network Europe, an incorporation of the European Technology Platform (ETP) for communications networks and services which follow the evolution of European policies in Horizon Europe. Emphasis is also made on the UK5G Use Cases. Also, the Big Data Value Association offers relevant information on the European public private partnership for ensuring trustworthy, safe and robust AI and related regulations. The webinar ends with highlights regarding standardization challenges in artificial intelligence and machine learning.

One of the key insights shared was the impact of AI on resource allocation. Dynamic and real-time allocation of network resources, facilitated by AI algorithms, ensures optimal utilization and responsiveness. This is crucial not only for enhancing user experience but also for supporting the diverse requirements of emerging technologies, including the Internet of Things (IoT), augmented reality, and mission-critical applications.

Also, with regards to 5G Security, Network Europe highlighted the significance of AI in addressing the evolving security challenges associated with advanced networks. AI-powered threat detection, anomaly identification, and predictive analytics contribute to creating robust cybersecurity frameworks, ensuring the integrity and confidentiality of data transmitted over 5G and 6G networks.

The integration of AI in 5G and the forthcoming 6G networks is a complex process that requires careful standardization and regulatory considerations. By addressing interoperability, QoS, privacy, security, ethics, and other key aspects, the industry can harness the full potential of AI-driven applications, creating a connected and intelligent future.

Relevance to the VITAL-5G Project

The relevance of this event for the VITAL-5G project is related to the Dynamic Resource Allocation with regards to the 5G network and the idea is to take into consideration AI techniques for various 5G network optimizations such as Dynamic Network Slicing. Also, Cybersecurity techniques for 5G networks using AI techniques was of relevance for the project - there are some chapters describing the 5G security of the VITAL-5G platforms in other WPs.

4.1.2. StandICT - 7th Talk & Walk Webinar on Women in ICT Standards

A webinar focusing on the role of women within the ICT Standardization landscape participation and contributions on Standards & Certification committees and activities (across a broad range of ICT areas) as part of the diversity, equity, and inclusion policy for the development of standards with a view to shape a world where everyone is adequately represented regardless of race or gender.

In this Webinar, representatives from various European and International Standards Developing Organizations talk about their current activities, effort and achievements with the broader scope of encouraging more women to participate in standardization.

One of the presenters was Fiona Delaney, founder of On Chain Networks, a startup focusing on Open source, Open data and Open innovation, who is active mostly in the standardization of Distributed Ledger Technology with contribution to ISO, ITU and IEEE.

The next topic is about EU NLF and Harmonized Standards by Sabine Janning (IBM) who talks about the NLF (New Legislative Framework) and the coevolution between EU Directives (requirements for a specific sector) and Harmonized European Standards (essential requirements, cross sector).

The NFL has the following requirements: Risk management system, Data and data governance, technical documentation, record keeping, transparency and provision of information to users, human oversight and accuracy, robustness, cybersecurity.

In the next section, a IETF representative talks about the organization's role in developing standards with a specific application on the Internet of Things vertical, including a presentation of their online resources on how to write a draft of a standard for a future proposal.

The founder of Flying Binary, a company that discusses about their implication in the standardization field by a BSI Standards Publication: Smart Cities – Guide to establishing a decision-making framework for sharing data and information services.

Relevance to the VITAL-5G Project

This webinar is of relevance for VITAL-5G's standardization efforts by the following subject: the IETF's presentation of their online resources on how to write a draft of a standard for a future proposal in the context that VITAL-5G as a consortium has to present / submit a standardization proposal to an SDO WG as part of our standardization efforts.

4.1.3. 5G-SOLUTIONS - Broadcaster Standardization Workshop

The 5G-SOLUTIONS project partners include Standards Developing Organisations, such as 3GPP SA, CTA and RAN working Groups, and IETF, as well as many other initiatives. An assurance that the expectations of the project will be fulfilled, in terms of adoption of standards and mainstream solution for the preparation of 5G services, was provided by the participation of these partners. The 5G-SOLUTIONS is focusing on proactive approach in project execution through a series of relevant planning actions.

5G-SOLUTIONS collects requirements for use in other projects, to be forwarded or checked with the SDOs, but it is an active project that contributes to the Standards. 5G-SOLUTIONS objective is the same as other EU funded projects: to have a positive impact on the EU society. February 2nd 2022, was when the workshop about standardization and broadcasters took place. The goal was to confirm that what is written in 3GPP matches the requirements of the project.

General information and the presentations are available on the web page of the 5G-SOLUTIONS project, also reachable from the following direct link [2].

During the workshop, the high-level architecture, use cases and roadmap were presented.

Figure 5: 5G-SOLUTIONS High Level Architecture.

As can be seen from the above diagram, 5G-SOLUTIONS leverages components from other ICT-17 EU Projects like 5G-EVE or 5G-VINNI. Regarding the Standardization activities, the project’s contributions to 3GPP Rel. 18 were presented.

Valuable information on the 5G-SOLUTIONS Standardization methodology was revealed during the workshop such as the Process flow identified in order to influence SDOs activities and disseminate within the project the main results of SDOs.

Figure 6: 5G-SOLUTIONS Process flow for SDO interaction.

Also, during the workshop, requirements to 3GPP were listed and these include:

1. The usage of Living Labs, a mix of “deterministic networks” “non-deterministic networks”:
 - a. a mix of “deterministic communications” and “non-deterministic communications”
 - b. static and dynamic network configuration.
2. A mixture of UE classes and traffic characteristics (present in every Lab).
3. The presence of Network management and orchestration of multi-tenant networks.

For disambiguation purposes, “deterministic networks” are ones in which served applications may generate traffic every X ms and require transmission delay stable within certain bounds and “non-deterministic networks” are ones in which static network configurations are present, which implies configurations that stay fixed for a

sufficiently long period of time: fixed number of Ues and gNBs, without mobility (E.g.: sensor network in a production line).

Going into detail regarding the 3 above points, proposals from were:

1. The parallel and simultaneous management of deterministic and non-deterministic networks, which implies:
 - i. The identification and management a “deterministic” slice
 - ii. Optimization of the deterministic slice performance in the conditions that the devices are not geographically moving and.
 - iii. The traffic pattern is known in advance
 - iv. Devices support apps that require both deterministic and non-deterministic communications.
2. Improve upload throughput and the life cycle of Ues in the Living Labs is 5-10 years
 - i. A significant number of Ucs have required high UL speeds and must operate in macro-cells with DL unbalanced frame structure.
 - ii. Usually, user equipment is not power limited for static use cases.
 - iii. UE is most of the time power limited for mobile devices.
 - iv. The UE should be future proof in order of radio frequency and 5G protocol stack compatibility.
 - v. The design of the UE must also be compatible with Transport and Core Network requirements.
3. Ensure network management in a multi-tenant environment
 - i. The usage of Open Interfaces for Network Management functions.
 - ii. Multi-tenant network environments to support the orchestration of radio resources.

Relevance to the VITAL-5G Project

The relevance of the 5G-SOLUTIONS workshops for the VITAL-5G project is that it sheds light on various 5G elements such as the orchestration engine, that are being standardized helping us better understand the various aspects of the entire standardization process while also providing valuable information on the new features of future 3GPP releases.

4.1.4. 5G-SOLUTIONS - Standardization Online Workshop

This 5G-SOLUTIONS webinar was a standardization information packed course, focused on and divided into 3 main topics:

- 5G-SOLUTIONS requirements submitted to 3GPP
- Rel18 main activities
- Rel 19 – initial content

Getting into more detail, the above concepts imply:

- The management of deterministic and non-deterministic networks
 - The identification and management of a deterministic slice.
 - Deterministic slice performance optimization (for immobile devices and known traffic patterns).
 - Device compatibility with deterministic and non-deterministic communications.
- Upload throughput improvements
 - Certain UE scenarios are not power limited thus can have better upload speeds.
 - Some UEs are power limited and for those, the DL/UL unbalance will remain.
- Living Labs lifecycle

- UEs should be upgradeable over the air.
- UEs should be compatible with the core network.
- Multi-tenant environment
 - The API exposure of Network Management Functions.
 - Orchestration by the network operator on multiple clients' environments.

Going forward, a snapshot of the 3GPP Rel. 17 and Rel. 18 was presented, updated June 2022.

Rel 17 not yet stable – commercial implementations based at earliest on Sep 22 version
 Rel 18 commercial products expected end of 2024/mid 2025

Figure 7: 3GPP Release 17 and 18 Roadmap.

In the following section of the webinar, there were presented an extensive list of approved project activities, their 3GPP reference number, the activity type and the type, as more details can be seen in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Radio Aspects: 3GPP Approved Activities.

Moving to the next section, SA2 prioritized Study Items for Rel. 18 were presented.

These included topics like:

- MIMO Evolution for Downlink and Uplink.
- Study on expanded and improved NR positioning.

- Study on further NR RedCap UE complexity/cost reduction.
- Study on XR Enhancements for NR.
- SA aspects: eXtended Communication capabilities.
- NR NTN (Non-Terrestrial Networks) enhancements.
- NR Support for UAV.
- Artificial Intelligence SA aspects: AI/ML (AI)/Machine Learning (ML) for NG-RAN.

Of importance for the 5G-SOLUTIONS project was the subject MIMO Evolution for Downlink and Uplink. More details in the below figure.

Figure 9: 5G-SOLUTIONS requirement – MIMO Evolution for Downlink and Uplink.

The following aspects were mentioned: the service requirement phases has just started, 12 studies by 3GPP SA1 have been agreed, Rel. 19 Stage 1 80% of normative to be ready by Jun0065 2023 and freeze in September 2023; more Architecture, Security, Codecs, Network Management System Activities to be agreed upon in 2023; RAN features to be defined by September 2023 - planning under discussion, completion deadlines to be provided.

Also in this section, a comprehensive list of SA1 Rel. 19 Studies was presented and it included the following topics: Study on Integrated Sensing and Communication; Study on Ambient power-enabled Internet of Things; Study on Mobile Metaverse Services; Study on roaming value added services; Study on Energy Efficiency as service criteria; Study on Upper layer traffic steering, switching and split-over dual 3GPP access; Study on AI/ML model transfer – Phase 2; Study on Network Sharing Aspects; Study on network of service robots with ambient intelligence; Study on satellite access - Phase 3; Study on UAV Phase 3; Study on FRMCS Phase 5; Study on Supporting Railway Smart Station Services.

All of the above were registered as 3GPP Technical Reports or TRs.

Relevance to the VITAL-5G Project

This second 5G-SOLUTIONS workshop focused on subjects of interest for both our project and our standardization efforts, such as: The identification and management of a deterministic slice, deterministic slice performance optimization, API exposure of Network Management Functions, Orchestration by the network operator on multiple clients' environments.

4.1.5. OSM13 Ecosystem Day

The VITAL-5G platform has been presented by Nextworks at the OSM13 Ecosystem Day² (June 15th, 2022), highlighting the adoption of ETSI OSM as reference NFV Orchestrator for the three VITAL-5G testbeds, the integration of OSM in the VITAL-5G system and the OSM features which are used in VITAL-5G for onboarding, provisioning, monitoring and configuration of Network Applications.

The screenshot shows the Open Source MANO website navigation bar with options: Main, Documentation, Hackfests, Community, Outreach. Below the navigation bar, a list of events is displayed, including a presentation by Nextworks at 4:50 - 5:10 pm CEST titled "Experimenting with NetApps for Transport & Logistic in 5G testbed". The abstract describes the VITAL-5G project's development of an open platform for automated provisioning, monitoring, and testing of NetApps for Transport and Logistic (T&L) services over three 5G testbeds in Athens, Antwerp, and Galati. It highlights the use of ETSI OSM as a reference NFV orchestrator and the integration of OSM in the VITAL-5G system for onboarding, provisioning, monitoring, and configuration of Network Applications.

The presentation slide shown in the screenshot is titled "OSM#13 Ecosystem Day - Nextworks" and "NetApps Definition and Tools". It features a video player with a play button and a VITAL 5G logo. The slide content includes:

Network Applications (NetApps)

A NetApp is a 5G-enabled virtual application which provides its own set of functionalities when deployed as a stand-alone entity and that can cooperate and interact with other NetApps to deliver more complex vertical services. NetApps extend the concept of VNFs declaring (i) service level information to simplify their re-usage, sharing and composition in vertical services and (ii) mobile connectivity requirements in terms of 5G network slice profiles or consumed 5G core services to automate their instantiation in 5G network virtual infrastructures.

NetApps tools:

- NetApp packages and NetApp blueprints to distribute and describe NetApps characteristics
- NetApp catalogue in VITAL-5G Open Online Repository, to onboard, discover and browse NetApps for building T&L vertical services
- Validation tools to verify NetApps, wizards and intent-based interfaces to build NetApp-based services and experiments
- Tools for automated testing and experimental validation to evaluate NetApps performances in configurable 5G networks

Slide 7

Figure 10: VITAL-5G at OSM#13 Ecosystem Day.

In this event, the Network Application concept and the information model of the Network Application blueprint have been presented to the OSM community. The focus has been on the enhancements to the information currently available in traditional VNFDs that are needed to declare Network Application requirements in terms of 5G mobile connectivity and services. This enables the automated creation or selection and configuration (depending on the capabilities of the 5G network management system available in each testbed) of the required network slices to complement the service provisioning offered by OSM. In this context, the format of the Network Application package and blueprint adopted in VITAL-5G has been presented, with examples related to available Net-Apps. Moreover, the VITAL-5G architectural components and the workflow for on-boarding and provisioning Network Application-based services have been analysed showing the complementarity and the interactions between (a) the VSB and Network Application Catalogue of the VITAL-5G platform and the VNFD and NSD catalogue in OSM and (b) the Service Lifecycle Manager of VITAL-5G and the provisioning component of OSM, mediated through the REST API offered by OSM. The slides and the video of the presentation are available on the web page of the OSM Ecosystem Day, also reachable from the following [3][4].

² [https://osm.etsi.org/wikipub/index.php/OSM13 Ecosystem Day](https://osm.etsi.org/wikipub/index.php/OSM13_Ecosystem_Day)

As adopter of OSM Orchestrator, VITAL-5G is also listed in the OSM Ecosystem – Research page ³.

Relevance to the VITAL-5G Project

The smooth integration between the VITAL-5G platform and OSM confirms the overall alignment between the VITAL-5G system design and the architectures, interfaces and information models defined in ETSI NFV ISG, which are at the basis of the ETSI OSM orchestrator. In fact, the approach used in VITAL-5G is based on Network Application-oriented enhancements to standard data models and platform components specialized for the Network Application-related additional logic while relying on standard NFV Orchestration functions (integrated via standard API) for the basic provisioning and lifecycle management procedures. This alignment with the ETSI NFV standard is expected to facilitate the potential integration (after the project termination) of the VITAL-5G platform with other testbeds with similar ETSI NFV-based architectures, even if deploying different types of NFV Orchestrators.

4.1.6. ETSI NFV Plugtests 2021

Orange was involved as an observer to the ETSI NFV & MEC IOP Plugtests [5], which took place remotely between 1-15October. This is a yearly event, organized by ETSI Center for Testing and Interoperability as part of the NFV Plugtests Program. Its aim is to bring together NFV and MEC solution providers and open-source projects who can test and review various technologies as well as the interoperability of their NFV and MEC solutions. It is also an opportunity to test the specifications of Network Applications and APIs.

The NFV&MEC IOP Plugtests 2021 was focused on verifying interoperability across different implementations of the main components of the NFV and MEC Architectural Frameworks, including:

- Virtual and Containerized Network Functions (VNF)
- Management and Orchestration (MANO) solutions, including integrated or standalone NFV Orchestrators (NFVO) and VNF Managers (VNFM)
- NFV infrastructure (NFVI) and Virtual Infrastructure Managers (VIM) in some cases providing Container Infrastructure Services and Services Management (CIS and CISM)
- MEC Applications, MEC Platforms and Systems

In addition, participants were offered the opportunity to test their NFV and MEC API implementations via a Test Automation Platform running standardized NFV and MEC API Conformance Test Suites.

Figure 11: NFV&MEC Plugtests 2021 Certificate of Participation.

This ETSI event is in fact quite extensive and preparations begin a few months prior with setting up the environments. Registration is open to the yearly event. The Plugtest’s scope is to test several areas such as

³ <https://osm.etsi.org/wikipub/index.php/Research>

multivendor NFV and MEC interoperability and APIs conformance. In this year’s event there were involved 29 organization and 75 engineers from across the globe, as shown in the figure below. This event is highly conducive for collaboration between different entities and has helped put together 3 VIM&NFVI, 4 MEC platforms and other solutions as well as 7 open source communities for support with implementation challenges.

Figure 12: NFV&MEC Plugtests 2021 Participants.

In terms of tools, all information is stored on wiki pages and Slack groups are setup for efficient communication. All the implementations, the functions under test and the support functions are connected and accessible through a HIVE testing automation platform, which is useful for enabling execution of connectivity pre-checks, selection of test tools, configuration of test system with reporting and logging. VNF and MEC Apps and images are stored in a repository and docker registry hosted at ETSI.

The ETSI team is closely involved with supporting the participants, helping with any issues that come up and facilitating collaboration between participants across time zones. This allows for good results such as setting up MEC IOP testing with orchestration or the development, improvement of test automation platforms, validation of robot test suites. At the end of the event, a yearly Plugtests report is written, and this is fed back to ETSI NFV and MEC Industry Specification Groups.

We plan to participate as observers or be actively involved in NFV Plugtests 2022, depending on the capabilities of the VITAL-5G testbed until the next workshop.

Relevance to the VITAL-5G Project

Although VITAL-5G is a T&L focused project, it shares many of the technical concepts with other 5G projects. The relevance of this event for VITAL-5G is that, from a 5G perspective, we could observe the latest VNF, NFV, NFVO, VIM, NFVI and MEC platforms, systems and tools all in one place, in an integration exercise.

4.1.7. 5GPPP - 5G European Annual Journal 2021

5G PPP projects impact on Standards Development Organizations (SDOs) – (Technical Report, October 2020). This technical report summarizes the outcome of a 5G-IA Pre-Standardization Working Group survey on the achieved and planned impact of 5G PPP Horizon 2020 projects on Standards Development Organizations (SDOs). The ultimate goal of the survey was to identify weaknesses and strengths, preventing or facilitating the transfer of 5G PPP research results to standardization bodies. The report includes the highlights from the survey, as contributed by 5G PPP projects on a voluntarily basis. It also summarizes main conclusions which will be a valuable input to improve the impact on standards of the next EU Research Framework Program.

Covid-19 also had an impact on standardization. In March 2020, 3GPP cancelled all in person Working Group (WG) and Technical Specifications Group (TSG) meetings. Release 16 Stage 3 freeze was delayed by 3 months until June 2020. 3GPP reached a consensus in December 2020 that remote working would be the norm until June 2021. The proposed date for Stage 3 Release 17 shifted to December 2021 and was further delayed to June 2022 in December 2020. Release 18 package Approval is scheduled for early 2022.

5G EVE achieved the opening of two Work Items in ETSI INT on the KPIs monitoring and validation. The action backed and promoted by the project has got wide support also among other partners in ETSI and represents a good success in the standardization footprint of the project.

Relevance to the VITAL-5G Project

This Journal is of relevance to the VITAL-5G project in the sense that the VITAL-5G Consortium would learn from other success stories of other EU projects regarding standardization initiatives. This will help the VITAL-5G Consortium in its objective to initiate a standardization proposal as a Work Item within an SDO WG or add to existing SDO WGs Work Items.

4.1.8. Merging 5Gi and 3GPP specifications

The Center of Excellence in Wireless Technology, along with the Institute of electronics in Madras and IIT Hyderabad have designed the local design of the 5G Radio Interface Technology called 5Gi.

The technology is an alternative in the future to the global 5G standards. The opposite of 5G is 5Gi's range at a lower Frequency. The latter can be used between the 700 and 52,000 MHz bands.

One of the promises of 5Gi is that it can make sure they don't have a lag between the advancement of 5G enabled rural areas and cities.

The adoption of 5Gi can be an issue for telecom companies as the infrastructures deployed by them will need to be re-engineered and re-deployed to support the 5Gi standards which will imply higher costs (usually local bands will be incompatible with the global 5G network).

The merger of 5Gi into 5G was approved in December 2021 by 3GPP and TSDSI (India's Telecom SDO) with specific milestones set for both. Many TSDSI member companies as well as global cellular vendors and multiple operators support the framework and steps to be taken to facilitate the intended merger according to the TSG RAN contribution (RP-213532).

Two change requests clarifying the specifications of the Pi/2-BPSK modulation scheme are technically endorsed from the 3GPP side. The objectives of the work item and recent way forward for the same project have been changed. TSDSI has committed to merger of 5Gi into 3GPP with a plan to pursue merged 3GPP 5G specifications in India.

In order to make the merger of 5Gi into 3GPP feasible, TSDSI is pursuing a plan to make 3GPP 5G specifications compulsory in India. This includes no further 5Gi specification submissions to the ITU-R.

The merger of 5Gi with 3GPP has made a single radio access proposal a reality, as well as enabling a single common specification for the 'IMT.2020' 5G family of standards (ITU-R).

CRs endorsed by TSDSI will be approved and implemented by 3GPP in the Rel-17 NR specifications once communication is received regarding the completion of the pertinent actions by TSDSI. These are under implementation in the TSG RAN Plenary meetings.

To conclude, the merger of the 5Gi set of standards into the 3GPP standardization framework will allow for a common specification as well as a single radio access proposal which will lead to better device to telecom networks compatibility throughout all regions [6].

Relevance to the VITAL-5G Project

This topic provides insights on how 3GPP standards evolve from one iteration to another as well as observing a standard merging procedure (“a single common specification for the ‘IMT.2020’ 5G family of standards”).

4.1.9. ITU Plenipotentiary Conference 2022 (PP-2022)

VITAL-5G participated as an observer in the ITU Plenipotentiary Conference (ITUPP 2022), which, as stated on its website (<https://pp22.itu.int/en/>), is “ITU’s highest policy-making body, that meets once every four years to set the Union’s general policies, adopt the four-year strategic and financial plans, and elect the senior management team of the organization, the Member States of the Council, and the members of the Radio Regulations Board.

This is a major opportunity to connect with relevant standardization organizations and use the experience gained from our attendance to successfully lead the effort for the submission of a standardization proposal.

The conference took place this in 2022 (PP-22) in Bucharest, Romania, from the 26th of September to the 14th of October 2022”.

Figure 13: VITAL-5G will participate as an observer in the ITU Plenipotentiary Conference due to take place in Bucharest, Romania from the 26th of September until the 14th of October 2022

Relevance to the VITAL-5G Project

This event is a great opportunity for VITAL-5G to observe the standards evolution processes. During the event, members of the consortium were present in multiple meetings, observing how standards documents are appended or modified in real time.

4.1.10. Projected SDO Monitoring Activities

As a continuation of our Standardization Contributions effort, additionally, we intend to monitor and report on various SDOs and their WGs of specific interest to the VITAL-5G project but also to standardization in the 5G and T&L sectors.

An example of the type of activities that we will be monitoring until the end of the project is presented below. The list includes relevant events, articles, webinars, seminars, workshops:

- 5G Standards in 3GPP,
- High-Level Considerations on Rel-18 Package,

- The ETSI standards making process and how to get involved in ETSI, ETSI OPEN SOURCE MANO LAUNCHES RELEASE TWELVE WITH ENHANCED NETWORK FUNCTION RESILIENCY AND RUNTIME OPERATIONS [27]
- Intent-driven cloud management for VDI and 5G-slicing services [28]
- World Telecommunication Standardization Assembly (ITU),
- ITU Kaleidoscope 2022,
- Maritime mobile service including Global Maritime Distress and Safety System (GMDSS); aeronautical mobile service and radiodetermination service (ITU),
- 5G-PPP White Paper: Beyond 5G/6G KPIs and Target Values,
- Research Results Impacting B5G and 6G through Standardization, EuCNC, June 2022,
- 3GPPP Release 17 SA,
- Evolution towards 5G-Advanced,
- Press Release: “Release 17 timeline agreed”,
- News story on “5G in Release 17 – strong radio evolution”,
- An Overview of 5G Advanced Evolution in 3GPP Release 18 [29]
- Evolution towards 5G-Advanced.

4.2. Monitoring of Transport & Logistics SDOs

In this subchapter the focus is on monitoring the activities of the T&L related SDOs, the main focus being on the organizations that have relevant input for the VITAL-5G project.

The current approach, as stated before with the 5G SDO monitoring activities is to participate at standardization related events of these organizations and participate in focus groups (open to any T&L company) or even in existing SDO work groups.

4.2.1. Digital Container Shipping Association Track and Trace Standards

DCSA and its member carriers have published track and trace (T&T) standards for the global container shipping industry. The T&T standards comprise of a common set of data, interface as well as processes that can be implemented by shippers, carriers, or third-party entities to enable cross-carrier shipment tracking. After implementation of the above-mentioned standards, partners or customers or any other active entities within the T&L landscape will be able to communicate with all carriers in a common way.

The data model ensures track and trace data definitions are consistent for all users, leveraging any system. These definitions are based on the Industry Blueprint, published by DCSA and its carrier members since 2019, which established a consistent vocabulary and proposed current state standards for industry processes.

The T&T container tracking standards are also aligned with the UN/CEFACT (United Nations Center for Trade Facilitation and Electronic Business) standards to ensure existing investments are preserved while streamlining communication among all supply chain participants.

Track & Trace OpenAPI Specifications

The API definitions of Track and Trace have been published by the DCSA on an open-source API development platform called SwaggerHub, from which carriers will be able to use these standardized libraries in order to quickly implement DCSA compliant APIs for customer facing track and trace requirements.

As part of the Track & Trace standard, DCSA has also published API definitions for the Track & Trace on SwaggerHub, an open–source API development platform. Carriers can use these definitions to rapidly implement DCSA standard-compliant APIs for customer-facing track and trace events.

Technical documentation on the Track and Trace standards can be found on GitHub, on their dedicated webpage.

Figure 14: GitHub portal of the Track and Trace DCSA OpenAPI specification.

Also, carriers which have implemented the Track and Trace API can be seen on the DCSA API Portal [7].

The recommended standards for tracking and tracing cargo within the international shipment phases (pre-shipment, pre-ocean, ocean, post-ocean, post shipment) can be viewed in the Track and Trace publication section, also available at [8].

By using the Track & Trace standards, customers will be able to easily track all shipping phases across all nine carriers that have implemented Track and Trace.

Relevance to the VITAL-5G Project

The relevance of these API standards to the VITAL-5G project is that the Track & Trace standardized APIs resemble the APIs (E.g. slice_conf) that we are in the process of developing between the VITAL-5G platform and the subsequent testbeds. Learning from how SDOs have defined standardized APIs is of VITAL importance for developing our own flexible APIs that could be used not only by our testbeds but for any other T&L related platforms.

4.2.2. GS1 Identifiers: Tag Data Standard

The Tag Data Standard (GS1 TDS, current release 1.13 of Nov 2019) defines various Electronic Product Code (EPC) identifiers, including the structure of barcodes and the memory contents of Gen 2 RFID Tags. It covers a large variety of identifiers and defines the format of each one.

GS1 identifier allocation is delegated to:

- GS1 national organizations, and further to:
- Client companies through a “company prefix”. Each company can freely allocate identifiers within its prefixes. TDS identifiers have fixed width but are split into variable-length fields. Usually, bigger companies get a shorter prefix, so they can allocate more identifiers within that prefix.

This is similar to the organization of the Domain Name System:

- IANA decides on the Top-Level Domains (TLD) such as .com, .eu, .info, .biz and country domains such as .bg, .uk, etc.
- Management of TLDs is delegated to domain registrars

- After a company obtains a domain (eg ontotext.com), it is free to allocate host names within that domain (eg www.ontotext.com, graphdb.ontotext.com, platform.ontotext.com)

TDS covers all kinds of objects that participate in a logistics supply chain:

- Individual objects, such as:
 - Physical and electronic individual goods or services
 - Coupons and business documents
 - Containers, palettes and other returnable assets
 - Railroad cars, marine vessels
 - Shipments and consignments
 - Sensors and other assets
- Classes of goods and services (GTIN)
- Lots or batches of goods
- Organizations that produce, ship, store and transport goods
- Places ranging from ports to individual ship berths, gates, company headquarters to warehouses, loading docks to individual doors, and even GPS locations

Relevance to the VITAL-5G Project

In order to identify a T&L component (API) that can be standardized, VITAL-5G must be aware of the standardization techniques / existing standardized communication protocols within the T&L sector.

4.2.3. GS1 Global Product Classification

The GS1 Global Product Classification (GPC) is a system that gives both sides of trading partner relationship a common language for grouping products in the same way. It ensures that products are classified correctly and uniformly, everywhere in the world. The term “product” as used throughout this guide refers mainly to physical products; however, GPC is expanding into services as well.

The business objectives of GPC are to:

- Support buying programs by allowing buyers to pre-select groups of applicable products
- Provide a common language for category management, thus speeding up reaction to consumer needs
- Be a key enabler of the Global Data Synchronization Network
- To be a Pivotal classification system between the information exchange parties

The GPC Schema Principles include:

- The GPC schema provides an optional four-tier hierarchy; segment, family, class and brick (GPC bricks may be used independently without the hierarchy). The hierarchy should be easy to understand/follow and balanced in order to facilitate search.
- Each level of the schema is determined by rules and/or principles, and also industry decision. However, the rules applied differ depending on the hierarchy level.
- The business rules apply to all levels or entities of the schema.
- Each brick may be assigned one or more attributes; in turn each brick attribute has a set of associated mutually-exclusive brick attribute values.

Sources:[9][10][11].

Relevance to the VITAL-5G Project

As a T&L related project, VITAL-5G must have awareness on the standardization techniques within the T&L sector.

4.2.4. EPCIS and CBV

EPCIS and CBV are complementary specifications that enable trading partners to share information about the physical movement and status of products as they travel throughout the supply chain – from business to business and ultimately to consumers. They help answer the “what, where, when and why” questions to meet consumer and regulatory demands for accurate and detailed product information.

- EPCIS defines supply chain events, enabling disparate applications to create and share visibility event data, both within and across enterprises
- CBV provides definitions of data values to be used to populate the data structures defined in EPCIS

EPCIS and Core Business Vocabulary Implementation Guideline introduces these standards and how to implement them.

Figure 15: Supply chain and EPCIS” visibility”.

As described in Figure 16, a simple supply chain and the EPCIS “visibility” are illustrated. Also, events generated along the way:

- The goods are manufactured and a product is packaged into cases which are in turn packed onto pallets.
- The products are shipped by truck from the manufacturer’s factory to the retailer’s distribution center.
- The products arrive at the retailer’s distribution center (DC) and are received into inventory.
- The products are shipped from the retailer’s distribution center by truck to the retail store.
- The products arrive at the retail store and are received into the stockroom.
- The products are moved from the stockroom (“back office”) to the sales floor (“front office”).
- In the retail store the product will be sold to the consumer.

The EPCIS specification is organized in 3 layers:

- Profiles

- EPCIS for Rail Vehicle Visibility
- EPCIS for Fighting Illicit Trade
- Case Studies
 - How EPCIS enables product visibility from source to shelves
 - How EPCIS is improving the safety of healthcare supply chains
 - Messaging Document: EPCIS – Improving traceability, security, and regulatory compliance
 - Case Study: GS1 application standard for visibility in rail
 - EPCIS: Enabling visibility with real time information on supply chain events

Figure 16: EPCIS organization.

EPCIS 2.0

The current version of the EPCIS standard is EPCIS 2.0, which adds support for:

- Sensor data for monitoring the condition of assets (e.g., in cold chains) and industrial IoT processes
- Certification details pertaining to products, organizations and locations
- Linked, browsable online definitions for all event data fields and classes, code lists and values
- JSON / JSON-LD syntax which is developer-friendly
- REST API for capture and query of event data, easing integration of EPCIS into evolving applications
- GS1 Digital Link URI syntax to express GS1 identifiers within EPCIS event data

Relevance to the VITAL-5G Project

The relevance of the EPICS framework for the VITAL-5G project is related to the REST API design / architectures / integrations and also the JSON file structures used by this framework. The idea is that some of this information is used in the design and structure of VITAL 5G's APIs - the VITAL-5G platform is using REST APIs with JSON format.

5 Standardization Contributions to SDOs

As initially decided within the consortium and stated in the Y2 project review, the scope of this chapter is to identify at least one Standardization Proposal and describe the identified Standardization Proposal.

After thoroughly analyzing the VITAL-5G end to end architecture, we have identified a VITAL-5G platform component which to consider for a Standardization Proposal: **the API for the management of network slices on the interface between the VITAL-5G platform and the network slice management system deployed at the various sites.**

In order to better illustrate the contribution of each partner of the VITAL-5G consortium, within the Standardization Contributions to SDOs, we have sketched the below table:

Table 3: VITAL-5G SDO Contributions.

Standardization Contributions to SDOs	Contributors	Comments - Contribution description
5.1 Description of the Component (API) This chapter describes the VITAL-5G component identified for a standardization proposal.		
5.1.1 Slice_conf 5G Network Functions and Functionalities	ORO	Describes the component to be standardized within the End to End Slicing Mechanism of VITAL-5G.
5.1.2 Slice_conf interface within VITAL-5G Unified SBI Architecture	ORO	Describes the component to be standardized as part of the VITAL-5G Unified SBI Architecture.
5.1.3 Slice_conf interface within the VITAL-5G E2E facility architecture	ORO	Describes the component to be standardized as a component of the VITAL-5G E2E facility architecture
5.1.4 Slice_conf interface within VITAL-5G Functional Blocks and Interfaces Architecture	ORO	Describes the component to be standardized in the VITAL-5G Functional Blocks and Interfaces Architecture
5.2 Description of the VITAL-5G platform component to be Standardized In this chapter, we take the component identified to be standardized and we describe it in detail.		
5.2.1 Slice_conf API and 3GPP Standards	ORO	We describe the component as it is now in the 3GPP standards.
5.2.2 3GPP TS 28.531 for REST API to create Network Slice Instances Standard Details	ORO	We describe the platform component as it is now in the 3GPP standard using the REST API technology.
5.2.3 3GPP TS 28.541 for the information model on network slices	ORO	Description of the platform component information model as it is now in the 3GPP standard.

5.2.4 Standardization Procedures of the 3GPP and 3GPP SA5 Management, Orchestration, Charging	ORO	A description of our efforts understanding the procedures of submitting a standardization proposal.
5.2.5 Slice_conf specific details and implementation status	ORO	The state of development of the VITAL-5G component that we aim to standardize.

5.1 Description of the Component (API)

In this chapter we aim to describe the component which we consider as being suitable for a standardization proposal.

The identified interface is **Slice_conf** and its high-level functions of the is to get the list of network slice instances, get network slice instance information, configure User Equipment for network slice instances and perform lifecycle (create/remove/update) of slice instances where the testbed and use cases permit such implementations.

The API endpoint is described from multiple perspectives, such as: VITAL-5G E2E facility architecture, VITAL-5G Unified SBI Architecture, VITAL-5G Software Architecture while also briefly describing the E2E slicing system and required network resources.

5.1.1 Slice_conf 5G Network Functions and Functionalities

In terms of 5G System and network resources the VITAL-5G slicing mechanism consists of the following elements, Table 4:

Table 4: 5G Slicing System and Network Resources.

5G NF	RAN	Core	Transport	MEC
Slicing	APN NSSAI/SST	APN NSSAI/SST	QoS DSCP MPLS	E2E slicing

As can be seen from the above table, the 5G Network Function used for slicing uses APN / NSSAI/SST in RAN and Core, DSCP for QoS and MPLS for Transport and E2E slicing in Multi-access edge computing.

In terms of Slice_conf main functionalities, the following table provides relevant information, Table 5.

Table 5: Slice_conf Interface Main Functionalities.

Testbed system	Interface	VITAL-5G Platform Component	Main functionalities

5G Slice Management System	Slice_conf	Multi-site 5G Slice Inventory	Get (filtered) list of network slice instance Get network slice instance information Configure UEs for a network slice instance Create/Remove/Update network slice instance (optional, valid for testbed where on-demand network slice provisioning is supported)
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5.1.2 Slice_conf interface within VITAL-5G Unified SBI Architecture

Each testbed has its own interfaces and orchestrators (NFV MANO), as well as network slice management systems and monitoring platforms. A common interface for all platform components is presented in the unified SBI at the VITAL-5G platform level.

The VITAL-5G testbeds, which are seen as black boxes by the VITAL-5G Platform, make use of specialized plugins which bridge the gap between their heterogenous specialized systems, and the unified data stream required by the platform.

The translation of testbed specific protocols and messages is performed using specific adaptors that translate the messages exchanged on the Mon_Conf, Mon_pub, Slice_conf, Nfvo_lcm, and Nfvo_cat interfaces.

Figure 17: Slice_conf interface in VITAL-5G Unified SBI Architecture.

The 5G Slice Management System API (or Slice_conf interface) is the API which allows the VITAL-5G platform to manage the network slices on the VITAL-5G testbeds or testbed sites. It encompasses network slice management capabilities for provisioning, configuration, termination, update, query of Network Slices. The interface (Slice_conf interface) is described in [24], and it is currently under implementation in the ORO lab for a subset of methods.

The above figure also shows that the VITAL-5G testbeds are SBI consumers of the VITAL-5G platform data streams with regards to the slice management section. Triggers for slice management are performed at testbed level.

5.1.3 Slice_conf interface within the VITAL-5G E2E facility architecture

The 5G communication services that need to be provided to the T&L industry can be seen in the innovative solution and implementation framework of the VITAL-5G E2E facility architecture model.

The model is also trying to bridge the gap between the existing Telco verticals and their subsequent segregated infrastructures by using methods like flexible network services deployment (in terms of dynamic resources and time allocation for services deployment / change / uninstall, easy integration through common APIs) and the deployment of specific vertical Network Applications (standalone or interacting with other Network Applications) all in live T&L dedicated networks.

Figure 18: Slice_conf within VITAL-5G E2E facility architecture.

The Slice_conf API is part of the 5G Infrastructure E2E and Orchestration functional block as each sub-block is related to the End-to-End methods for transferring data on standardized 5G architectures (in this case the 5G SA 3GPP Rel. 16 architecture).

5.1.4 Slice_conf interface within VITAL-5G Functional Blocks and Interfaces Architecture

In this section the Slice_conf interface is described in the context of the VITAL-5G Functional Blocks and Interfaces Architecture. To be more specific, the architecture is made up of hardware and software elements that power various 5G network elements. All testbeds are 3GPP Rel.16 compliant with the same 5G features and capabilities, but using different technologies such as different IaaS services, cloud implementation principles or virtualization solutions, but regardless of the differences at the testbed level, the VITAL-5G architecture supports E2E network slicing, enhanced slice management, orchestration, and automation functionalities.

To be more specific, the below diagram, (Figure 19) illustrates that the testbeds are using different RAN, Transport, Core, Virtualization technologies and common components such as the Orchestration component or interfaces with the VITAL-5G platform (the APIs between Testbeds and the VITAL-5G platform).

Figure 19: Slice_conf within the VITAL-5G Functional Blocks and Interfaces Architecture.

Within this architecture approach, the Slice_conf interface is part of functional block A (a concept defined in D 1.2, Chapter 7.2 Services and interfaces offered by VITAL-5G Facilities).

The A-Interface (Slice management as depicted in Figure 17 above) is the interface which provides basic slice management information, using GET functions to retrieve the 5G slicing characteristics to each testbed and the slicing must be manually configured, depending on the Slice/Service Type (SST) specifications.

5.2 Description of the Standardization Proposal

The main objectives of this chapter are (1) to describe the 3GPP standards on which the Slice_conf interface was designed and (2) pass through the 3GPP standardization proposal procedure of a Standardization Proposal to 3GPP under SA5 Management, Orchestration and Charging.

5.2.1 Slice_conf API and 3GPP Standards

As stated in [33], the API interface’s technical specifications are based on two underlying 3GPP standards, and the implementation of the interface is under way, based on [31] for the information model on network slices, Table 6

Table 6: VITAL-5G slice management.

Testbed system	Interface	Reference standards	Implementation
5G Slice Management System	Slice_conf	3GPP TS 28.531 for REST API to create Network Slice Instances 3GPP TS 28.541 for the information model on network slices	Implementation in progress.

5.2.2 3GPP TS 28.531 for REST API to create Network Slice Instances Standard Details

The 3GPP TS [30] for REST API to create Network Slice Instances standard is about describing API based approach by the 3GPP for the Network Slices lifecycle management (four phases: preparation, commissioning, operation, and decommissioning).

The NSI lifecycle stage implies the following functions: Create an NSI, Activate an NSI, De-active an NSI. Modify an NSI. Terminate an NSI.

Going further into detail, each phase in the lifecycle of the NSI use one or more of the above-mentioned states as shown in Table 7.

Table 7: NSI Phases according to 3GPP TS 28.531 for REST API.

Commissioning phase	Operation phase	Decommissioning phase
Create an NSI; Activate an NSI; De-active an NSI; Modify an NSI; Terminate an NSI.	Create an NSI	Activate an NSI; Modify an NSI; De-active an NSI.

The above table shows the NSI lifecycle stages and its subsequent operations.

Configuration Information for both NSI and NSSI are the same and include the following:

- Information on the requirements to be applied to every NSI constituent to satisfy the requirements of multiple NSIs.
- Network function selection information (depending on the NSI, can be AMF or other).
- Connection information (carry CP or UP data between NFs and NSSIs within the NSI).

Regarding General Information, we use a table again (Table 8 Slicing general information) in order to better illustrate the differences between what the NSI and the NSSI can hold as General Information according to the [30] for REST API to create Network Slice Instances standard.

Table 8: Slicing general information.

	Interface	Management model information	Capability model information
NSI	network slice type (E.g., eMBB) additional system feature (e.g., multicast, Edge Computing) priority	information model that is used for network slice lifecycle management configuration profile	supported communication service characteristic information (e.g., service type, UE mobility level, density of users) QoS attributes (e.g., bandwidth, latency, throughput) capacity (e.g., maximum number of UEs)

	QoS attributes (e.g., bandwidth, latency, number of subscribers) NSD ID		Can be exposed to CSC
NSSI	Network slice type (e.g., eMBB) additional system feature (e.g., multicast, Edge Computing) priority	information model that is used for network slice subnet lifecycle management configuration profile	supported communication service characteristic information (E.g. (e.g., service type, UE mobility level, density of users) QoS attributes (e.g., bandwidth, latency, throughput) capacity (e.g., maximum number of Ues)

In terms of Network Slice Journey, a possible approach could be using the NsaaS model. The high-level call flow is presented in Figure 20:

Figure 20: Network Slice journey (NsaaS model) – High-Level Call Flow.

The NsaaS model, as in [12][13] implies the following steps:

- 1) A Network Slice Customer sends a request to NSP’ BSS, ordering a network slice instance to a Network Slice Provider, depending on the NSP’s product offering.
- 2) The NSP’s BSS receives the NSC request and translates NSC specifications into NSP technical parameters.
- 3) NSP’s OSS is triggered by the NSP’s BSS to provide an NSI which fits the NSC specifications.
- 4) As a result of the NSC request, the NSP Provisioning MnS creates a new NSI or assigns an existing NSI.
- 5) The NSP’s Network Slice Provisioning MnS requests the NSSI corresponding to the NSI from the Network Slice Subnet Provisioning MnS.

- 6) One or more NSSIs may have to be created by the NSP’s Network Slice Subnet Provisioning MnS depending on the service required.
- 7) The required VNFs and PNFs are configured by the NSP’s Network Function Provisioning MnS

5.2.3 3GPP TS 28.541 for the information model on network slices

In 3GPP [31]for the information model on network slices standard encompasses data on concepts such as:

- The Network Resource Model (NRM) for NR, NG-RAN, 5G Core Network (5GC) and network slicing.
- The behavior of management interfaces class attributes or relations from a technology and protocol agnostic standpoint, encompassed in the NRM Information Model.
- The NRM Solution Set, which defines protocol specific solutions for the Information Model on NRM.

Information model of the Network Resource Model

Regarding the Information Model of NRM, the standard specifies the following Class Diagrams, in terms of Relationship between modules and inheritance.

Figure 21: Network slice NRM Relationship Diagram.

Figure 22: Network slice NRM Inheritance Diagram.

The <<OpenModelClass,Preliminary>> NetworkService is a collection of VNFs and PNFs that create the underlying layer for the <<InformationObjectClass>> NetworkSliceSubnet module

In line with the table specified in chapter 5.2.1, Table 4: 5G Slicing System and Network Resources, the IOCs (Information Object Classes) of relevance for our particular slice_conf interface would be the following:

- NetworkSlice
- NetworkSliceSubnet
- ServiceProfile <<dataType>>
- SliceProfile <<dataType>>

NetworkSlice – covered in [30], it represents the properties of a network slice instance in a 5G network, including the below attributes, Table 9.

Table 9: Network Slice IOC Attributes.

Attribute name	Support Qualifier	isReadable	isWritable	isInvariant	isNotifyable
operationalState	M	T	F	F	T
administrativeState	M	T	T	F	T
serviceProfileList	M	T	T	F	T
nSSIId	M	T	F	F	T

* M = Mandatory; T = True; F = False

NetworkSliceSubnet – also covered in [30], this IOC encompasses the properties of a network slice subnet instance in a 5G network, as in Table 10.

Table 10: IOC network slice subnet instances.

Attribute name	Support Qualifier	isReadable	isWritable	isInvariant	isNotifyable
mFldList	M	T	F	F	T
constituentNSSIIdList	M	T	F	F	T
operationalState	M	T	F	F	T
administrativeState	M	T	T	F	T
nsInfo	CM	T	F	F	T
sliceProfileList	M	T	T	F	T

* M = Mandatory; CM = Conditional-Mandatory; T = True; F = False

Both NetworkSlice and NetworkSliceSubnet inherit attributes from the SubNetwork IOC, defined in [32], as for more information about the network slice subnet instance, see [30].

The NetworkSliceSubnet IOC includes attributes inherited from SubNetwork IOC (defined in TS 28.622) and the following attributes: ServiceProfile <<dataType>> - the requirements that should be supported by the NSI in the 5G network, as in Table 11.

Table 11: NetworkSliceSubnet IOC attributes from SubNetwork IOC.

Attribute name	Support Qualifier	isReadable	isWritable	isInvariant	isNotifyable
serviceProfileId	M	T	F	T	T
sNSSAList	M	T	T	F	T
pLMNIdList	M	T	T	F	T
perfReq	M	T	T	F	T
maxNumberOfUEs	O	T	T	F	T
coverageAreaTAList	O	T	T	F	T
latency	O	T	T	F	T
uEMobilityLevel	O	T	T	F	T
resourceSharingLevel	O	T	T	F	T
sST	M	T	T	F	T
availability	M	T	T	F	T

* M = Mandatory; O = Optional; T = True; F = False

NRM Solution Set Definitions

From the perspective of the NRM Solution Set Definitions, the standard specifies State Handling rules as well as data formats to be used in 3GPP Rel. 16 deployments.

NSI vs NSSI State Handling

In terms of State Handling, in the following section we present the similarities and differences between an NSI and an NSSI. This information will further help us in our standardization efforts.

Both an NSI and an NSSI are logical objects which represent virtual or physical resource grouping with various states, within an NMS which, at all times must be aware of the states of the NSI and NSSI.

The existing states, as defined in ITU-T X.731 and in systems theory in general, are: the operational state, the administrative state and the usage state.

Figure 23: Combined NSI vs NSSI state diagrams.

When it comes to the state transition triggers, the below, side-by-side state diagrams show the various states through which the NSI and the NSSI can transition to and from.

Figure 24: NSI vs NSSI state diagram with state transition triggers.

Considering the above diagrams in 27 and 28, at first glance, the states look very similar, but going a little more in depth, one can see that there are some differences between NSI and NSSI in terms of the deployment scenario.

In terms of operation, the NSI and NSSI state transition events and actions are more or less the same as can be seen in the below table, seen in Table 11.

Table 12: NSI vs NSSI state transition events and actions.

Trigger number	The state transition events and actions	The state transition events and actions
0	NSMF responds positively to the "Create NSI request" message, the NSI is created and the state is set to Locked	NSSMF responds positively to the "Create NSSI request" message, the NSSI is created and the state is set to Locked
1	NSMF responds positively to the "Activate NSI request" message (identifying the NSI to be activated). ----- or -----	NSSMF responds positively to the "Activate NSSI request" message (identifying the NSSI to be activated). ----- or -----

	CM operation to set administrative state to Unlocked.	CM operation to set administrative state to Unlocked.
1a	CM Operation to set administrative state to Unlocked	CM Operation to set administrative state to Unlocked
2	The last user of the NSI stops using the NSI	The last user of the NSSI stops using the NSSI
2a	CM Operation to set administrative state to Shutting down	CM Operation to set administrative state to Shutting down
3	When the NSI and its constituents are installed and working NSMF receives positive response to the "Allocate NSSI" message (applicable to the NSI to be enabled).	When the NSSI constituents are installed and working NSSMF receives positive response to the "Create NSSI constituent" message (applicable to the NSSI to be enabled).
4	When the NSI or its constituents are not installed or not working NSMF receives positive response to the "Deallocate NSSI" message (applicable to the NSI to be disabled)	When the NSSI constituents are not installed or not working NSSMF receive positive response to the "Delete NSSI constituent" message (applicable to the NSSI to be disabled)
5	NSMF responds positively to the "Deallocate NSI request" message, the NSI is deleted and the state is set to NULL	NSSMF responds positively to the "Delete NSSI request" message, the NSSI is deleted and the state is set to NULL.

What differs between the NSI and NSSI transition states is the level at which the NSI and the NSSI operate. For example, the NSI, operating at a higher level, operates with the NSMF and "allocates" or "deallocates" NSSIs, while at the NSSI level, we have NSSMF instead if the NSMF and NSSIs are "created" or "deleted". The CSMF, NSMF and NSSMF are all standardized.

Data Formats

The data related to the slice_conf interface, according to the current standard can be represented in XML, JSON or YANG formats. Using the same format within the entire network can provide better end to end compatibility, also seen in [14][15][17][18][19][20][21].

Below, a few examples of data formats with regard to our interface.

Examples of XML, JSON and YANG formats, with methods of relevance for the slice_conf interface, in List of Annexes.

5.2.4 Standardization Procedures of the 3GPP and 3GPP SA5 Management, Orchestration, Charging

In order to submit a Technical Report or a Technical Specifications request to the 3GPP, one must undergo the specific steps underlined by the organization in the multiple information brochures referenced in this chapter.

Also, the scope of this chapter is to raise the VITAL-5G consortium's awareness of the procedures that need to be followed in order to try and submit a standardization proposal by the end of the project.

The responsibilities of the 3GPP Technical Specification Groups (TSGs) are: 3GPP release content and time planning elaboration and monitoring; approving, maintaining and developing Technical Specifications or Technical reports; the coordination of WGs in which Technical Specifications or Technical Reports are created, modified or removed / i.e. the entire lifecycle management of standards.

Figure 25: The 3GPP Standardization Process.

Also, after successfully submitting a TS or TR to a 3GPP WG, the person that submits it is elected to be the "rapporteur" of that TS or TR which basically means that the person who submits it is a "center of knowledge" on the subject. As a result, the 3GPP or the broader technical community can ask questions to the "rapporteur" on the TS or TR and also any modification is the responsibility of the responsible which has submitted the initial document. Moreover, the 3GPP can ask the "rapporteur" to make regular updates to the TR or TS submitted.

Considering that the 3GPP technical specifications were mostly based on the initial GSM specifications, for maximum compatibility between GSM and UMTS / LTE / 5G networks standard specifications it was decided that the same format as the ETSI object identifiers would be used. Also, both ETSI and 3GPP are recognized under the same ISO arcs, both for Internet protocol specifications standardization.

To be eligible for issuing a TS or a TR within one of the 3GPP WGs one must first participate in the relevant WGs. Currently, the list of active TSGs (Technical Specifications Groups) are:

TSG RAN - Radio Access Network

- RAN WG1 - Radio Layer 1 (Physical layer)
- RAN WG2 - Radio layer 2 and Radio layer 3 Radio Resource Control
- RAN WG3 - UTRAN/E-UTRAN/NG-RAN architecture and related network interfaces
- RAN WG4 - Radio Performance and Protocol Aspects
- RAN WG5 - Mobile Terminal Conformance Testing

TSG SA - Service & System Aspects

- SA WG1 - Services
- SA WG2 - System Architecture and Services
- SA WG3 - Security and Privacy
- SA WG4 - Multimedia Codecs, Systems and Services
- SA WG5 - Management, Orchestration and Charging
- SA WG6 - Application Enablement and Critical Communication Applications

TSG CT - Core Network & Terminals

- CT WG1 - User Equipment - Core Network protocols
- CT WG3 - Interworking with External Networks & Policy and Charging Control
- CT WG4 - Core Network Protocols
- CT WG6 - Smart Card Application Aspects

Considering the above active WGs and the specificities of the **slice_conf** interface, the most suitable WG to which the consortium could consider submitting a standardization proposal is the SA WG5 Management, Orchestration and Charging.

The SA WG5 - Management, Orchestration and Charging is one of the WGs of 3GPP TSG SA which covers Technical Specifications (both functional and service oriented) on subjects such as Management, Orchestration and Charging for 3GPP systems, as the current responsibilities of the TSG SA WG5 are:

- Architecture, service and data definitions for Management, Orchestration and Charging requirements, solutions and protocol specific definitions.
- Operation, fulfillment, automation, interaction management with network operator external entities.
- CDR (Charging Data Records) and Quota Management aspects as they relate to the Service Provider and End User.
- Supporting new services for public or non-public networks in aspects covering Management, Orchestration and Charging
- Coordinate on Management, Orchestration and Charging with other 3GPP WGs on relevant Standards Developing Organizations (SDOs), Market Representation Partners (MRPs) and Open-Source communities.

The 3GPP specifications are recurrently published four times a year after the quarterly Technical Specification Group (TSG) plenary meetings.

At each TSG round, specs can be:

- New documents, under change control which should be completed 80% or more.
- Specifications not changed since last version.
- Updated documents at release-freeze time, updated to the latest release with no changes.
- Updated documents as a result of Change Requests.

Below, some considerations regarding the document format, copyright standards and further document modification. The Spec templates are in Microsoft Word version 2000 format, i.e. .doc files because of some technical limitations of the .docx format. Also, other software packages that can work with .doc document format are usable. The skeleton of the document must be kept as is and the Introduction clause can be deleted if no introduction is needed. Another specific element is that the 3GPP specs are divided in clauses and not chapters. The first 3 clauses are mandatory to be kept and information must be inserted in to these as per requirement (1) Scope, (2) References, (3) Definitions. From clause 4 onwards, the specifications sheet ToC is up to the applicant

to customize as needed. Also, when referencing 3GPP specs from different releases, the release version must be specified (E.g. Rel 15). Also, when referencing multiple specs, each spec must be specified and no reference to a group of specs must be made. In accordance with copyright standards, documents can be referenced but text must not be copied into the specification. Copying and pasting from any documents that are not public is accepted but this must undergo editorial revision to make sure the information is not presented as a work of the author's (except for the situation in which the author of the standardization proposal is also the author of the nonpublic source document). Sometimes a part of the references might become deprecated as some in which case the deprecated references must be removed from the document. The deprecated reference must be replaced with "(void)" and the number of the former reference be kept. Any modification to the accepted 3GPP standardization proposals must be done via a Change Request. This includes removing deprecated references. Clauses can have sub-clauses. The recommended number of sub-divisions of a clause is 6.

We are currently in the phase of familiarizing with the document templates and complex procedures of the 3GPP and for the next period we intend to add the specific **slice_conf** information of relevance for the standardization proposal and submit it by the end of the VITAL-5G project timeline, aligned to [16],[26], [27], [28], [29], [30].

5.2.5 Slice_conf specific details and implementation status

The specificity of the **slice_conf** interface is that, while in the underlying 3GPP standards (which have been covered in the previous chapters of the document), the focus is more on slice provisioning, the VITAL-5G management interface focuses more on configuration operations.

Currently, the **slice_conf** interface is implemented in the ORO lab, between the VITAL-5G platform and the ORO testbed, for a subset of operations.

These are:

1. Adding a subscriber to a JSON file (usually used by the popular REST interfaces), adding a slice name and description, an IMSI and a 5G profile using the CLI command: `<< cat test_sub_with_PUT.json >> .`
2. An API call of the JSON file defined at point 1. The subscriber is provisioned in the 5G UDM/UDR using the following command:
`<< curl --include -k -L -X PUT 'https://{IP}:30106/apc/v2/udr/1/udr/subscribers/<name>' -T name.json -H "Content-Type: application/json" >> .`
3. Displaying the existing subscribers, their slice name, description, IMSI and 5G NGC profile, by using the following API call: `<< GET https://{IP}:30106/apc/v2/udr/1/udr/subscribers >>.`

An example of an API call and response (Point 1 from above), for creating a json file in which to put the Subscribe IMSI, define a name and attach the 5G profile), described in Table 13.

Table 13: Slice_conf API Call IMSI Subscription.

API Call IMSI Subscription
<pre>{ "name": "5G_SA2_21", "description": "5G_SA", "uiccs": [{ "imsi": "226:10:7900000080",</pre>

```
        "ngc-profile": "eMBB2"  
    }  
}
```

More details on the above-mentioned API calls and their responses in **Annex 2: API Call Examples**, as in [22][23][24][25].

6 Conclusions

This section is summarizing the outputs of the deliverable and how it has contributed to the overall project's objectives and goals, as here applicable, to identify business impact, map business benefits with VITAL-5G's innovative offerings and record user evidence, to move into standardization the project achievements and benefits.

Several specific actions into standardization effort have been presented, starting for the SDOs monitoring activities, vertical's mapping into the standards, technologies achievements supporting and promoting the 5G implementations and validation, results achieved through intensive experimentations. The specific presented actions, activities described and contribution are concluding the path in the standardization efforts. We have contributed in several aspects, as main achievement being the mapping of the APIs and described interfaces into the 5G reference architecture, the interaction between the defined project VITAL-5G platform and open 5G testbeds.

Based on the 1st half of project activities and achieved developments, we have identified several potential future standardization and improvements next steps, as for the delivery of D6.3 "Report on standardisation activities" we intend to continue the effort by focusing on one the following actions:

- Identifying possible synergies with WP5 patenting activities (what is patentable might also be standardisable).
- Finalize the Standardization Proposal described in D 6.5 Report on Standardization – Intermediate, follow the Standards Submission Procedure of the SDO and submit a Standardization Proposal to an SDO.
- Participate in more SDO Working Groups.
- Exploring the possibility to actively participate in an event like ETSI NFV Plug tests (usually an event that takes place every 2 years) and have the opportunity to test the VITAL-5G platform (including its components that could be standardisable) and its vertical agnostic capabilities (one of the objectives of such events is "to accelerate the standards-making process").
- Identify new VITAL-5G components that could be standardised (as the VITAL-5G platform develops, platform elements that were concepts are implemented for research or commercial purposes).

7 References

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- [32] 3GPP TS 28.622, “Universal Mobile Telecommunications System (UMTS); LTE; 5G; Telecommunication management; Generic Network Resource Model (NRM) Integration Reference Point (IRP); Information Service (IS)”, V16.4.0, August 2020

List of Annexes

ANNEX 1: NRM Solution Set Definitions Data Formats

XML format

Within the 5GC, XML schema "ngcNrm.xsd".

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>

<!--
  3GPP TS 28.541 5GC Network Resource Model
  XML schema definition
  ngcNrm.xsd
....
<complexType name="NfProfile">
  <sequence>
....
    <complexType name="NfProfile">
  <sequence>
    <element name="nfInstanceId" type="string"/>
    <!-- nfInstanceId is uuid of NF instance -->
    <element name="nfType" type="ngc:NfType"/>
    <element name="nfStatus" type="ngc:NfStatus"/>
    <element name="plmn" type="en:PLMNId"/>
    <element name="nfType" type="ngc:NfType"/>
    <element name="sNssais" type="ngc:SnsaiList"/>
    <element name="fqdn" type="string"/>
....
type="ngc:DefaultNotificationSubscriptions"/>
    <element name="allowedPlmns" type="en:PLMNIdList"/>
    <element name="allowedNfTypes" type="ngc:NfTypeList"/>
    <element name="allowedNssais" type="ngc:Nssai"/>
    <element name="capacity" type="string"/>
    <element name="supportedFeatures" type="string"/>
....
<simpleType name="NfType">
  <restriction base="string">
    <!-- NF name is defined in TS 23.501 -->
    <enumeration value="NRF"/>
    <enumeration value="UDM"/>
    <enumeration value="AMF"/>
    <enumeration value="SMF"/>
    <enumeration value="AUSF"/>
```

```

<enumeration value="NEF"/>
<enumeration value="PCF"/>
<enumeration value="SMSF"/>
<enumeration value="NSSF"/>
<enumeration value="UDR"/>

```

....

```

<complexType name="UpfInfo">
  <sequence>
    <element name="snssaiUpfInfo" type="ngc:SnssaiUpfInfo"/>
  </sequence>
</complexType>
<complexType name="SnssaiUpfInfo">
  <sequence>
    <element name="sNssai" type="ngc:SNssai"/>
    <element name="dnnUpfInfoList" type="ngc:DnnUpfInfoList"/>
  </sequence>
</complexType>

```

....

```

<complexType name="SnssaiList">
  <sequence>
    <element name="sNssai" type="ngc:SNssai"/>
  </sequence>
</complexType>
<complexType name="SNssai">
  <sequence>
    <element name="sst" type="ngc:Sst" minOccurs="0"/>
    <element name="sd" type="ngc:Sd"/>
  </sequence>
</complexType>

```

....

JSON format

Examples of JSON modules at 5GC.

```

{
  "openapi": "3.0.1",
  "info": {
    "title": "3GPP 5GC NRM",
    "version": "15.3.0",
    "description": "OAS 3.0.1 specification compatible schema for 3GPP 5GC NRM"
  },
  "paths": {},
  "components": {

```

```
"schemas": {  
  
....  
"sNssais": {  
    "$ref": "nrNrm.json#/components/schemas/Snssai"  
  
....  
"allowedNssais": {  
    "type": "array",  
    "items": {  
        "$ref": "nrNrm.json#/components/schemas/Snssai"  
  
....  
"ManagedNFProfile": {  
    "type": "object",  
    "properties": {  
        "nfInstanceID": {  
            "type": "string"  
        },  
        "nfType": {  
            "$ref": "genericNrm.json#/components/schemas/NFType"  
        },  
        "authzInfo": {  
            "type": "string"  
        },  
        "hostAddr": {  
            "$ref": "genericNrm.json#/components/schemas/HostAddr"  
        },  
        "locality": {  
            "type": "string"  
        },  
        "nFInfo": {  
            "$ref": "#/components/schemas/NFInfo"  
        },  
        "capacity": {  
            "type": "integer"  
        }  
    }  
  
....  
  
"AmfFunction": {  
    "allOf": [  
        {  
            "$ref": "genericNrm.json#/components/schemas/Top-Attributes"  
        },  
        {
```

```

    "type": "object",
    "properties": {
      "attributes": {
        "allOf": [
          {
            "$ref": "genericNrm.json#/components/schemas/ManagedFunction-Attributes"
          },
          {
            "type": "object",
            "properties": {
              "plmnIdList": {
                "$ref": "nrNrm.json#/components/schemas/PlmnIdList"
              },
              "amfIdentifier": {
                "$ref": "#/components/schemas/AmfIdentifier"
              },
              "sBIFqdn": {
                "type": "string"
              },
              "weightFactor": {
                "$ref": "#/components/schemas/WeightFactor"
              },
              "snssaiList": {
                "$ref": "nrNrm.json#/components/schemas/SnssaiList"
              },
              "amfSet": {
                "$ref": "genericNrm.json#/components/schemas/Dn"
              },
              "managedNFProfile": {
                "$ref": "#/components/schemas/ManagedNFProfile"
              }
            }
          }
        ]
      }
    }
  }
}

```

YANG format

Examples of YANG modules at 5GC.

`_3gpp-5gc-nrm-externalnssffunction.yang`

```

module _3gpp-5gc-nrm-externalnssffunction {
  yang-version 1.1;
  namespace urn:3gpp:sa5:_3gpp-5gc-nrm-externalnssffunction;

```

```

prefix extnssf3gpp;

import _3gpp-common-yang-types { prefix types3gpp; }
import _3gpp-common-subnetwork { prefix subnet3gpp; }
import _3gpp-common-top { prefix top3gpp; }
import _3gpp-common-managed-function { prefix mf3gpp; }

description "This IOC represents external NSSF function controlled by another management domain.";

revision 2019-06-11 {
    description "Ericsson refactoring.";
    reference "Based on
        3GPP TS 28.541 V15.X.XX";
}

grouping ExternalNSSFFunctionGrp {
    uses mf3gpp:ManagedFunctionGrp;

    list pLMNIdList {
        description "List of at most six entries of PLMN Identifiers, but at least one (the primary PLMN
        Id).
            The PLMN Identifier is composed of a Mobile Country Code (MCC) and a Mobile Network
        Code (MNC).";
        min-elements 1;
        max-elements 6;
        key "mcc mnc";
        uses types3gpp:PLMNId;
    }
}

augment "/subnet3gpp:SubNetwork" {
    list ExternalNSSFFunction {
        description "5G Core External NSSF Function";
        reference "3GPP TS 28.541";
        key id;
        uses top3gpp:Top_Grp;
        container attributes {
            uses ExternalNSSFFunctionGrp;
        }
    }
}

```

```
_3gpp-5gc-nrm-nssffunction.yang
```

```

module _3gpp-5gc-nrm-nssffunction {
  yang-version 1.1;

  namespace urn:3gpp:sa5:_3gpp-5gc-nrm-nssffunction;
  prefix nssf3gpp;

  import _3gpp-common-managed-function { prefix mf3gpp; }
  import _3gpp-common-managed-element { prefix me3gpp; }
  import ietf-inet-types { prefix inet; }
  import _3gpp-common-yang-types { prefix types3gpp; }
  import _3gpp-common-top { prefix top3gpp; }

  organization "3gpp SA5";
  description "This IOC represents the NSSF function in 5GC. For more information about the NSSF, see
  3GPP TS 23.501.";
  reference "3GPP TS 28.541";

  revision 2019-05-15 {
    description "initial revision";
    reference "Based on
    3GPP TS 28.541 V15.X.XX";
  }

  grouping NSSFFunctionGrp {
    uses mf3gpp:ManagedFunctionGrp;

    list pLMNIdList {
      description "List of at most six entries of PLMN Identifiers, but at least one (the primary PLMN
      Id).
      The PLMN Identifier is composed of a Mobile Country Code (MCC) and a Mobile Network
      Code (MNC).";
      min-elements 1;
      max-elements 6;
      key "mcc mnc";
      uses types3gpp:PLMNId;
    }

    leaf sBIFQDN {
      description "The FQDN of the registered NF instance in the service-based interface.";
      type inet:domain-name;
    }

    leaf-list sNSSAIIList {

```

```
description "List of S-NSSAIs the managed object is capable of supporting.
    (Single Network Slice Selection Assistance Information)
    An S-NSSAI has an SST (Slice/Service type) and an optional SD
    (Slice Differentiator) field.";

reference "3GPP TS 23.003";
type types3gpp:SNssai;
}

leaf-list nSIIdListWrap {
    description "Set of NSI Ids. The NSI ID represents the Network Slice Instance Identifier.";
    //optional support
    type types3gpp:NsiId;
}

augment "/me3gpp:ManagedElement" {
    list NSSFFunction {
        description "5G Core NSSF Function";
        reference "3GPP TS 28.541";
        key id;
        uses top3gpp:Top_Grp;
        container attributes {
            uses NSSFFunctionGrp;
        }
    }
}
```

Annex 2: API Call Examples

Example 1

Adding a subscriber to a JSON file (usually used by the popular REST interfaces), adding a slice name and description, an IMSI and a 5G profile.

Call

```
[mcn@apc1-1 user]$ cat test_sub_with_PUT.json
```

Response

```
{
    "name": "5G_SA2_21",
    "description": "5G_SA",
    "uiccs": [{
        "imsi": "226:10:7900000080",
        "ngc-profile": "eMBB2"
    }]
}
```

Example 2

Subscriber activation of 5G services based on the input from Example 1.

Call

```
curl --include -k -L -X PUT 'https://{IP}:30106/apc/v2/udr/1/udr/subscribers/5G_SA2_21' -T test_sub_with_PUT.json -H "Content-Type: application/json"
```

Response

No specific CLI response. The subscriber is provisioned in the 5G UDM/UDR and can use 5G services according to the profile described in 1st Example.

Example 3

Display all existing subscribers and their adjacent 5G services.

In this case, multiple eMBB and URLLC slices have been defined and some subscribers are

Call

```
GET https://{IP}:30106/apc/v2/udr/1/udr/subscribers
```

Response

```
{
  "total-count": 21,
  "data": [
    {
      "name": "5G_SA2_10",
      "description": "5G_SA",
      "uiccs": [
        {
          "imsi": "226:10:7900000010",
          "ngc-profile": "URLLC-40M"
        }
      ]
    },
    {
      "name": "5G_SA2_11",
      "description": "5G_SA",
      "uiccs": [
        {
          "imsi": "226:10:7900000070",
          "ngc-profile": "eMBB2"
        }
      ]
    },
    {
      "name": "5G_SA2_12",
      "description": "5G_SA",
      "uiccs": [
        {
          "imsi": "226:10:7900000071",
          "ngc-profile": "eMBB2"
        }
      ]
    },
    {
      "name": "5G_SA2_13",
      "description": "5G_SA",
      "uiccs": [
        {
          "imsi": "226:10:7900000072",
          "ngc-profile": "eMBB2"
        }
      ]
    },
    {
      "name": "5G_SA2_14",
      "description": "5G_SA",
      "uiccs": [
        {
```

```
        "imsi": "226:10:7900000073",
        "ngc-profile": "eMBB2"
    }
]
},
{
    "name": "5G_SA2_15",
    "description": "5G_SA",
    "uiccs": [
        {
            "imsi": "226:10:7900000074",
            "ngc-profile": "eMBB2"
        }
    ]
},
{
    "name": "5G_SA2_16",
    "description": "5G_SA",
    "uiccs": [
        {
            "imsi": "226:10:7900000075",
            "ngc-profile": "URLLC-40M"
        }
    ]
},
{
    "name": "5G_SA2_17",
    "description": "5G_SA",
    "uiccs": [
        {
            "imsi": "226:10:7900000076",
            "ngc-profile": "URLLC-40M"
        }
    ]
},
{
    "name": "5G_SA2_18",
    "description": "5G_SA",
    "uiccs": [
        {
            "imsi": "226:10:7900000077",
            "ngc-profile": "URLLC-40M"
        }
    ]
},
{
    "name": "5G_SA2_19",
    "description": "5G_SA",
    "uiccs": [
        {
```

```
        "imsi": "226:10:7900000078",
        "ngc-profile": "URLLC-40M"
    }
]
},
{
    "name": "5G_SA2_20",
    "description": "5G_SA",
    "uiccs": [
        {
            "imsi": "226:10:7900000079",
            "ngc-profile": "URLLC-40M"
        }
    ]
},
{
    "name": "5G_SA2_5",
    "description": "5G_SA2",
    "uiccs": [
        {
            "imsi": "226:10:7900000005",
            "ngc-profile": "eMBB2"
        }
    ]
},
{
    "name": "5G_SA2_6",
    "description": "5G_SA2",
    "uiccs": [
        {
            "imsi": "226:10:7900000006",
            "ngc-profile": "eMBB2"
        }
    ]
},
{
    "name": "5G_SA2_7",
    "description": "5G_SA2",
    "uiccs": [
        {
            "imsi": "226:10:7900000007",
            "ngc-profile": "eMBB2"
        }
    ]
},
{
    "name": "5G_SA2_8",
    "description": "5G_SA2",
    "uiccs": [
        {
```

```
        "imsi": "226:10:7900000008",
        "ngc-profile": "eMBB2"
    }
]
},
{
    "name": "5G_SA2_9",
    "description": "5G_SA2",
    "uiccs": [
        {
            "imsi": "226:10:7900000009",
            "ngc-profile": "URLLC"
        }
    ]
},
{
    "name": "5G_SA_1",
    "description": "5G_SA",
    "uiccs": [
        {
            "imsi": "226:10:7900000000",
            "ngc-profile": "eMBB2"
        }
    ]
},
{
    "name": "5G_SA_2",
    "description": "5G_SA",
    "uiccs": [
        {
            "imsi": "226:10:7900000001",
            "ngc-profile": "URLLC"
        }
    ]
},
{
    "name": "5G_SA_3",
    "description": "5G_SA",
    "uiccs": [
        {
            "imsi": "226:10:7900000002",
            "ngc-profile": "eMBB2"
        }
    ]
},
{
    "name": "5G_SA_4",
    "description": "5G_SA",
    "uiccs": [
        {
```

```
        "imsi": "226:10:7900000003",
        "ngc-profile": "eMBB2"
    }
]
},
{
    "name": "5G_SA_5",
    "description": "5G_SA",
    "uiccs": [
        {
            "imsi": "226:10:7900000004",
            "ngc-profile": "eMBB2"
        }
    ]
}
]
}
```